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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the creation of the permafrost best practice guidelines as part of the WMO Guide No. 8. This document is a central achievement of Pilot Service 2, as well as for Arctic PASSION, since it provides the much-needed guidelines for a world-wide standardization of permafrost measurements. It even spans beyond Arctic PASSION's field of activity (i.e., Arctic), and also addresses permafrost measurements in the Third Pole Region, Antarctica and in high mountain regions. Scientists from the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P – office currently part of PS 2) were central in the development of the Permafrost Best Practices and the GTN-P community will be an important point for distributing the document, once it is published. World-wide permafrost measurement data is collected by the GTN-P community and consequently stored and made accessible in the GTN-P database. Losing access to data derived from measurements of permafrost in Russia is a tremendous loss for the entire scientific permafrost community and poses challenges to the understanding of the global development of permafrost temperature in light of climate warming. Satellite data coupled with modeling approaches will help filling this gap in the future but cannot fully replace in-situ permafrost measurements at present. Since the technology and modeling is still being developed, it is not part of this first version of the permafrost best practice guidelines. As the permafrost best practices will be published as part of the official WMO Guide No. 8, we expect it to have a long-lasting legacy effect.

Below is a copy of the official announcement on the WMO webpage, followed by the approved Permafrost Best Practices which will be published as Chapter 4 in the second volume of the Cryosphere Variables of the WMO Guide for Instruments and Methods of Observation. With a total of 81 pages and 12 figures, it was subject to WMO-internal, as well as external experts' revisions.

[WMO official announcement](#)

The 3rd session of the WMO Commission for Observation, Infrastructure and Information Systems (INFCOM-3) approved Chapter 4. Measurement of Permafrost, which is included in Volume II, Measurement of Cryosphere Variables, of the WMO Guide for Instruments and Methods of Observation (WMO-No. 8). This new chapter was developed by the Task Team on Permafrost of the Advisory Group on the Global Cryosphere Watch (AG-GCW), within the framework of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS) – Measurements. This achievement was made possible through collaboration with experts from GCOS, Global Network Terrestrial – Permafrost (GTN-P), and the International Permafrost Association (IPA).

At the opening of the INFCOM-3 session, the WMO Deputy Secretary General emphasized that "The degradation of permafrost is probably the largest negative feedback in the atmosphere, with significant, yet, not fully understood consequences of the increasing amount of carbon in the atmosphere; The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reported that the Arctic and boreal permafrost contain almost twice the carbon that is in the atmosphere today. The thawing of permafrost will likely lead to the largest irreversible process influencing climate warming and it will have broad consequences in terms of impacts on the water cycle and the need to strengthen national multi-hazard early warning systems." The newly approved chapter is the first internationally coordinated guide for the measurement of GCOS Permafrost ECV variables. These variables include permafrost temperature, active layer thickness, and rock glacier velocity. The guide covers common observation methods, the instrumentation used, the required configuration, and the relevant data reporting aspects. This guide will increase global standardization of permafrost observations and access to harmonized data to advance necessary scientific research, including supporting the implementation of other WMO flagship initiatives such as the Global Greenhouse Gas Watch (G3W).

CHAPTER 4. MEASUREMENT OF PERMAFROST

(Work in Progress by the Permafrost Task Team of the GCW Advisory Group)

Under the guidance of the GCW Advisory Group and in coordination with the GCW Best Practices Coordinator, the Permafrost Task Team developed the Permafrost Best Practices Guide. It will be included in the WMO Guide for Instruments and Methods of Observation (WMO-No. 8), Volume II, Measurement of Cryosphere Variables, as Chapter 4.

The guidelines cover measured variables, their common observation methods, the used instrumentation, the required configuration, and the relevant data reporting aspects.

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4.1 GENERAL

4.1.1 Introduction

Permafrost is defined as ground material which remains at or below 0 °C for at least two consecutive years, typically for long time periods and reaching considerable depths. It can be found in cold regions in polar and high-elevation areas on both hemispheres. Permafrost warming and thawing can have major consequences for the natural as well as human environment and impact ecosystems, and hydrological processes and landscape stability (Ward Jones et al., 2019; Liljedahl et al., 2016; Walvoord & Kurylyk, 2016). In the high-latitude permafrost regions, the latter affects slope instability in ice-rich permafrost (unconsolidated sediments) including active layer detachments and thaw slumps, typically found along stream and river valleys. This has implications for transportation corridors and ecosystems through impacts on water quality for example (ref). Thaw settlement associated with thawing of ice-rich permafrost is another example of landscape instability. In high-elevation areas ground instability affect the integrity of infrastructure built on permafrost or on steeper perennially-frozen slopes (e.g., Bommer et al., 2010; Duvillard et al. 2019, Hjort et al., 2022) and increases potential for geohazards such as rock falls or rock avalanches (Haeberli et al., 2017; Hock et al., 2019). In high-latitude permafrost areas, large amounts of carbon are stored in frozen organic matter that are decomposed and released as greenhouse gasses upon thawing, with the potential to impact the global climate system (Miner et al. 2022).

As a thermal subsurface phenomenon, permafrost reacts sensitively to changes in climatic conditions and thus was selected as one of the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) of the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (Belward et al. 2016, Bojinski et al. 2014). Decadal changes in the state of permafrost temperature have been used as indicators of climate change (e.g. Biskaborn et al. 2019, S. L. Smith et al. 2022). The Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) is the primary international programme concerned with the long-term monitoring of permafrost (Streletskiy et al. 2021). Permafrost monitoring relies on in-situ measurements because permafrost is a subsurface phenomenon. The key indicator variables (see S. Smith and Brown, 2009) observed to monitor permafrost long-term changes were defined as products of the ECV permafrost (defined in the GCOS Implementation Plan, Zemp et al. 2022) and are implemented within GTN-P (Streletskiy et

al. 2021). Standardization and strategic planning of permafrost monitoring are crucial to achieve consistent and comparable long-term records (e.g., Noetzli et al. 2021).

The methods and corresponding best practices to measure the three products of the Permafrost ECV – permafrost temperature, active layer thickness, and rock glacier velocity are described in this document (see Section 1.2 for their definition). It focuses on the methods most applied by the scientific community for the long-term monitoring of permafrost in the framework of climate observation:

- 1) The measurement of **permafrost temperatures** in boreholes is the direct and quantitative thermal observation of permafrost and the primary method for its long-term climate-related monitoring (see Section 4.2).
- 2) The measurement of the **active layer thickness** (ALT) reflects inter-annual changes in air temperature and snow conditions (see Section 4.3) in combination with heave and subsidence.
- 3) Variations in the viscous creep of perennially frozen ground – termed **rock glacier velocity** (RGV) – were shown to follow the changes in the thermal conditions and water contents in ice-rich permafrost and are used as an indirect observation of permafrost evolution, especially in remote mountain areas with difficult access (see Section 4.4). This variable is the most recent to have been included as a product of the ECV permafrost.
- 4) Additional variables are typically observed to characterize permafrost conditions in the framework of a research study or an infrastructure planning or a long-term monitoring project. Therefore, a set of **supplementary measurements** and existing guidelines and recommendations are described as well (see Section 4.5).

The guidelines and best practices for measurements of the key indicator variables of permafrost, i.e., the ECV products, were elaborated in coordination and collaboration with global and regional climate-related monitoring programmes, including the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P). Detailed local measurements are linked to global process understanding within the framework of the Global Hierarchical Observing Strategy (GHOST), which is linked to GTN-P (see Harris et al., 2001 for its application to permafrost monitoring). The Permafrost and Climate in Europe (PACE) project (Harris et al., 2001) and the Swiss Permafrost Monitoring Network (PERMOS, 2019; Noetzli et al., 2021) provided valuable details on mountain permafrost measurement approaches and instrumentation.

The best practice guidelines on permafrost agree with the Implementation Plan of the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) and the ECV requirements (WMO, 2022) of GCOS as well as with the measurement guidelines and recommendations for GTN-P (Streletsky et al., 2022).

1.1. 4.1.2 Definitions and variables

Permafrost: Ground material that remains continuously at or below 0 °C for at least two consecutive years.

Permafrost is defined on a thermal and temporal basis as ground with a maximum temperature of 0 °C throughout the year, typically for long time periods (centuries to millennia) and often reaching considerable depths (up to several 100 m). Permafrost can be found in polar and cold high-elevation regions on both hemispheres. Relict terrestrial permafrost can also extend offshore in the Arctic region. It became submerged after the last ice age and is currently degrading beneath the shelf sea above it. Even if permafrost is defined on its thermal state, its practical relevance and, thus, also the difference to non-permafrost ground, depends primarily on the presence of ice in the ground. With temperatures approaching 0 °C, permafrost can also contain significant amounts of unfrozen water, depending on the properties of the sediment grain size and pore fluid. Permafrost therefore can also be referred to as perennially cryotic ground. In addition to temperature, the geotechnical and hydrological characteristics of the subsurface can be significantly altered by pore- and excess ice (including ice lenses), ice-filled fractures and unfrozen water.

The layer above the top of the permafrost and subject to annual thawing and freezing is termed the **active layer** (Figure 4.1.1). In contrast to permafrost, the active layer is often defined based on the freezing point of water, which can be lower than 0 °C (see Section 4.3.1.1 for more information and definitions). The upper boundary of the permafrost below which ground temperatures remain at or below 0 °C is called the **permafrost table**. Due to the different thermal conductivities of thawed and frozen material in the active layer, the mean annual temperature at the permafrost table can be lower than the **mean annual ground surface temperature** (MAGST). This effect is termed **thermal offset**. The thermal offset means that permafrost can exist even in areas where MAGST is above 0 °C

(e.g., S. L. Smith et al. 2022). Ground temperatures typically increase with depth following the geothermal gradient, which is defined by the geothermal heat flux and thermal properties of the sediments or bedrock. Permafrost extends down to the **permafrost base**, below which ground temperatures are above 0 °C. The temperature profile can be influenced by different soil properties in the ground (e.g., Williams and Smith, 1989) as well as by three-dimensional effects of steep topography (Noetzli and Gruber 2009), and by changes in atmospheric and ground surface temperatures.

Near-surface ground temperatures fluctuate in response to high-frequency variations in air temperature and snow cover regime. The temperature variations experienced at the ground surface are attenuated and delayed with increasing depth. At the **depth of Zero Annual Amplitude (DZAA)** seasonal changes in temperature remain at or below 0.1 °C (e.g., French, 2017). Below the DZAA, temperature variations no longer reflect seasonal patterns but reflect long-term thermal changes, i.e., the climate signal.

When the active layer no longer freezes down to the permafrost table during winter due to increasing atmospheric and ground surface temperatures, an area develops that is unfrozen but underlain by permafrost, called a **talik**. Taliks also form beneath water bodies etc.

Figure 4.1.1. Schematic diagram of the equilibrium thermal regime of the ground and near-surface atmosphere in permafrost terrain. The mean annual ground temperature (MAGT) declines toward the temperature at the top of the permafrost (TTOP). The temperature envelope (shaded) between the ground surface and the depth of zero annual amplitude (DZAA) indicates the range of ground temperatures between the minimum (T_{min}) and maximum (T_{max}) during a year. MAAT, mean annual air temperature; MAGST, mean annual ground surface temperature. Image modified from one produced by Julian Murton.

Characteristic landforms and geomorphic processes in the landscape can be used as indicators of permafrost occurrence, such as rock glaciers, ice wedges, pingos, palsas, peat plateaus, patterned ground, solifluction lobes, etc. A **Rock glacier** (Figure 4.1.2) is defined as a debris landform generated by the former or current creep of frozen ground

(permafrost), detectable in the landscape with the following morphologies: steep front, lateral margins and sometimes ridge-and-furrow surface topography (RGIK, 2023a). Due to high ground ice content, which induces cohesion and reduces internal friction, the material contained in a rock glacier creeps and shows coherent flow fields. Rock glacier kinematics are controlled by a combination of environmental (i.e., internal structure, landform geometry, topography, geology, lithology and debris loading) and climatic factors (i.e., temperature, precipitation and snow, Arenson et al. 2002).

Figure 4.1.2. Rock glacier in the Vallone di Sorte (Italy) identified in the landscape by a front (discernable talus delineating the terminal part of the moving area perpendicular to the main flow direction), lateral margins in continuity of the front and localized ridge-and-furrow surface topography. Background imagery: Google Earth. Adapted from RGIK, 2023a.

1.2. 4.1.3 Permafrost distribution and characteristics

Permafrost presently underlies $\sim 16\text{--}21 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ of Earth's land surface, seafloor, and subglacial terrain (Murton 2021, Figure 4.1.3) and is found mainly in the Northern Hemisphere, but also in southern hemisphere mountain ranges and in Antarctica. Current estimates show that approximately 15% of the Northern Hemisphere is underlain by permafrost (Obu 2021).

Permafrost regions are traditionally divided into several zones based on estimated geographic continuity in the landscape. A typical **classification** (cf. Figure 4.1.3) recognizes continuous permafrost (underlying 90–100% of the landscape); discontinuous permafrost (50–90%); sporadic permafrost (10–50%), and isolated patches (0–10%). In the discontinuous and sporadic zones permafrost distribution is complex and patchy, and permafrost-free terrain is common. The **thickness of permafrost** varies from less than one meter to more than 1600 meters.

Most of the permafrost in polar areas existing today formed during cold glacial periods, and has persisted through warmer interglacial periods, including the Holocene (last 10,000 years). Some relatively shallow permafrost (30 to 70 meters) formed during the second part of the Holocene (last 6,000 years) and some during the Little Ice Age (from 400 to 150 years ago). In continental interiors permafrost temperatures at the boundaries between continuous and discontinuous are generally about $-5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding roughly with the isotherms of the $-8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ mean annual air temperature.

The distribution of permafrost is primarily a result of the surface energy balance, which is influenced by climatic conditions, as well as topography, surface and subsurface characteristics. The extreme topography of high mountain areas leads to extreme horizontal and vertical spatial variability (e.g., Gruber and Haeberli, 2009; Zhao et al. 2020) in these factors and, hence, to a highly heterogeneous permafrost distribution.

In mountain regions, permafrost is found in bedrock, debris slopes, viscous and ice-rich creeping features (rock glaciers), moraines, or glacier forefields. Further, gravity-driven downslope deformation processes are widespread (Noetzli et al. 2021). Ground ice content ranges from ice-rich terrain, oversaturated with massive ice (tens of meters thick) in loose debris to ice-poor bedrock with permanent ice only present in rock pores and fractures. In

mid-latitude mountains, such as the European Alps or the Central and Southern Andes, widespread permafrost regions have temperatures close to 0 °C, with considerable amounts of unfrozen water present in the soil matrix (Halla et al. 2021; Noetzli et al. 2021). In shady bedrock slopes at high elevations, however, permafrost can be as cold as in the high Arctic (Noetzli et al., 2019).

Subsea permafrost occurs close to 0°C over large areas of the Arctic continental shelf, where it formed during the last glacial period on the exposed shelf landscapes. Permafrost is geographically continuous beneath the ice-free regions of the Antarctic continent.

In general, the **active layer thickness** decreases poleward and increases in continental areas in response to changes in the mean annual temperature at the ground surface and its annual amplitude. The thickness will depend on geology (thermal conductivity of material), vegetation and snow cover. The thinnest active layers are commonly located at the highest latitude or at the highest elevation where permafrost is continuous. In these regions, active layer thicknesses are generally about 0.5 m to 1 m thick. However, some high Arctic maritime locations, especially those under the influence of warm ocean currents can have considerably warmer permafrost and a thicker active layer than other sites at comparable latitudes. The maritime areas may also receive a larger amount of precipitation compared to more continental locations resulting in higher accumulation of snow and hence a thicker active layer. For example, observations from the Circumpolar Active Layer Monitoring (CALM) program (Nelson et al., 2021) indicate that long-term ALT in a continuous permafrost zone of Alaska ranges from 0.3 to 0.7 m (Nyland et al., 2021) while in Svalbard, which is at higher latitude it is 1–2 m (Strand et al., 2021). In sub-arctic locations, the active layer can reach 2–3 m in thickness. In areas underlain by discontinuous and/or sporadic permafrost, the unfrozen layer (**talik**) can develop between the active layer and the top of permafrost when the layer that thawed in the summer does not completely refreeze in the winter. In alpine environments, the thickness of the active layer can be highly variable as well due to the complex interplay of factors controlling the distribution and characteristics of mountain permafrost.

At local and regional scales, ALT is highly spatially variable. Variations in topography, subsurface properties, soil moisture, and snow and vegetation cover modify the zonal pattern radically, resulting in a high degree of geographic variability. Several conceptual

examples of active layer development under similar climatic conditions can be considered (Bonnaventure and Lamoureux 2013): 1) A thick (few meters to ten meters) active layer develops in exposed bedrock due to its high thermal conductivities and low ice/water content. For example, in northern North America ALT of more than 10m has been observed in bedrock with high thermal conductivity (S. L. Smith et al. 2010) and the ALT ranges from about 1 to more than 10 m in the Swiss Alps and in the Norwegian mountains (Permos 2023; Etzelmuller et al. 2023). Variations in rock structure, surface temperature, and/or snow depth can result in significant thickening or thinning of the active layer in rock material: 2) an active layer of intermediate thickness (up to a few meters) can be found in well-developed mineral soils. In those soils, vegetation, soil texture, soil moisture, and ice content of the underlying permafrost, in addition to ground surface temperature and snow depth, control the spatial and temporal variability of the active layer thickness. 3) In permafrost environments with a thick organic mat (>10 cm), the active layer thickness is relatively small (from a few cm to a meter) due to the much lower thermal conductivity of mosses and peat in the thawed state than when frozen. As in other permafrost environments, changes in ground surface temperature and/or snow cover can promote changes in the active layer thickness. However, due to the thick protective organic mat, the active layer is slowest to respond to these changes. The contrast between mineral and organic-rich soils is apparent within the high latitude permafrost regions. In e.g., West Siberia ALT in sandy soil ranges from 1.4–1.7 m while in nearby peatlands from just 0.4–0.5 m (Oblogov et al., 2023).

Rock glaciers are found in all permafrost-affected mountain ranges worldwide. Rock glacier velocity observed at the surface typically ranges from a few centimeters to decimeters or meters per year and only occasionally exceeds annual displacements of three meters (Blöthe et al 2021). At a global scale a common trend of (multi-)decennial accelerating rock glacier velocities have been observed especially since the 2000's with regional variabilities in terms of onset timing and magnitude (Pellet et al. 2023). These can be interrupted by short-term periods of rock glacier stagnation or deceleration, particularly after snow-poor winters with efficient cooling and refreezing of ground water.

Figure 4.1.3. Permafrost zonation based on classified modeled permafrost probabilities (Obu et al. 2019). Subsea permafrost distribution was modeled with CryoGrid 2 (Overduin et al., 2019). Permafrost exists in steep slopes of mid-latitude high mountain regions such as the European Alps or the Andes, which is not well represented on this map. The permafrost zonation in the Tibetan Plateau is not well reproduced. In actuality, the plateau consists of extensive regions with discontinuous and sporadic permafrost, rather than continuous permafrost. Isolated patches of permafrost are not shown on this map. Map by GRID-Arendal/Nunataryuk, <https://www.grida.no/resources/13519>.

1.3. 4.1.4 Site selection – general considerations

The rationales for measuring permafrost parameters are diverse and can include long-term climate-related observations, detailed process studies of ecosystem, geologic or hydrologic

processes, an assessment of permafrost conditions prior to construction, or monitoring climate change impacts of the stability of existing infrastructure on permafrost. The specific objectives of permafrost observation should guide the selection of the location, the selection and spatial arrangement of the instrumentation, and/or the longevity of the observational site(s) needed. Detailed recommendations for selecting sites for monitoring specific permafrost parameters (e.g., permafrost temperature, active layer thickness) are provided in the corresponding sections of this document. Here, following Noetzli et al. (2021), we briefly outline general site selection criteria to be considered for establishing a monitoring network aimed at assessing climate-induced permafrost changes.

The **Relevance** of a site is defined by the ability of a new observational site to fill spatial gaps and/or temporal discontinuity in data records provided by existing observational networks. Geographic settings (e.g., bioclimatic regions, landscapes, topographic units) underrepresented in existing observational networks should be prioritized for site selection. The socio-economic relevance of the potential monitoring site(s), for example, to local populations including indigenous people, should also be considered.

The **Representativeness** of a location refers to how well site conditions (e.g., topography, landforms, surficial geology, edaphic properties, vegetation, or permafrost properties) represent a specific area and/or object of study. Locations for monitoring operated in the scope of long-term changes should reflect the most common characteristics of the area. Anthropogenic disturbance, artificial surfaces, and proximity to infrastructure can greatly alter the ground thermal regime and should be avoided for climate-related monitoring (e.g., Isaksen et al. 2000).

Feasibility and **longevity** relate to the accessibility of the site as well as to potential hazards or terrain deformation threatening equipment. It can be affected by changing climatic conditions, human activities, hazards and geopolitics (e.g., adverse world events that impact international collaboration and field access). The time frame of guaranteed site operation must be assessed, and appropriate resources allocated to ensure the continuity of observations.

It can be valuable to align sites along latitudinal, altitudinal, or continentality transects to assess bioclimatic or topoclimatic **gradients** (see Permafrost ECV Requirements - Spatial

distribution). Existing examples are the latitudinal transects of permafrost temperature (e.g. Osterkamp and Romanovsky 1999) and active layer (e.g Nyland et al., 2021) monitoring sites along the Dalton Highway/Trans Alaskan Pipeline in Northern Alaska, the network of sites in the Mackenzie Valley in Canadian Northwest Territories (e.g. S. L. Smith et al. 2010), the European PACE transect from Svalbard to the Sierra Nevada (Harris et al. 2001), the altitudinal transect on Dovrefjell in Southern Norway (Sollid et al. 2003), the transect along the Qinghai-Tibet highway and railway (e.g. Wu et al. 2010), or along the precipitation gradient from East to West of the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau Zhao et al. 2021).

For the final selection of an observation site, local permafrost conditions need to be assessed directly: active layer thickness, depth of permafrost base, permafrost temperatures, potential permafrost warming and deformation rates. Information may be derived at the site of interest or from proximate locations, based on permafrost distribution maps, geomorphological and geological maps, meteorological data, ground temperatures, geophysical surveys, ground characteristics, geology or geodetic surveys, and digital image analysis of slope deformation (e.g., Noetzli et al., 2021).

2. 4.2 MEASUREMENTS OF PERMAFROST TEMPERATURE

2.1. 4.2.1 General

4.2.1.1 *Definition, Units, Scales*

Permafrost temperature is the temperature measured in the permafrost at specific depths, typically along a vertical profile (Figure 4.2.1). The temperature measurement in a borehole is the primary and direct method to characterize permafrost thermal state and its changes. Permafrost temperature is measured in degrees Celsius (symbol: °C).

Permafrost temperature is commonly measured in a drilled borehole (see Section 4.2.2), either with a permanently installed sensor string in the borehole for continuous measurements by a data logger (see Section 4.2.3), or by temporary lowering of a portable temperature sensor into the borehole to measure the temperature at different depths (see Section 4.2.4). At some sites manual temperature measurements (without data logger) are done using a fixed multi-sensor cable in the borehole. The depth of the borehole and the

measurements depend on the purpose of the measurements, the estimated permafrost temperature and depth, the geology and subsurface materials, the terrain and its accessibility, the available drilling equipment, and financial resources (Noetzli et al., 2021). Typically, permafrost temperature is measured at multiple depths ranging from 1 m to 100 m. Most of the boreholes operational today are >2–30m deep. The temporal resolution and the spacing of the measurements along the profile in the borehole typically decrease with depth due to the decreasing temporal variability of the ground temperatures.

Parameters that can be derived from permafrost temperature profiles by inter- or extrapolation are the Active Layer Thickness (see Section 4.3), the DZAA, the permafrost base or the detection of taliks (see Figure 4.1.1). The annual ground temperature envelope can be derived from the minimum and maximum annual values in continuous temperature time series at each measured depth above the DZAA (Streletskiy et al., 2021). Also, the 0 °C isotherm in the ground can be derived by interpolating temperatures measured at different depths in a borehole, which is often used as a proxy for the ALT, particularly in terrain where other methods are not applicable (e.g., debris or bedrock ground, see Section 4.3.6).

Figure 4.2.1. Typical permafrost temperature time series and vertical temperature profiles from Janssonhaugen (78.18°N 16.47°E, 275 m a.s.l.), a permafrost monitoring station in Svalbard. a) Daily time series of ground temperature at 0.2, 1.6, 5 and 10 m depth. b) Ground temperature profile on 8 January 2024 (in blue). The past minimum, maximum, median, and confidence intervals for the same date during the monitoring period are shown in grey. c) Long-term changes in daily ground temperature at 10 and 20 m depth, with trends included. At 20 m depth, seasonal variations become negligible (corresponds to DZAA), making the temperature at this depth a suitable indicator of long-term change in permafrost thermal state. d) Mean annual ground temperature profiles from surface to 100 m depth. Updated figures available as operational permafrost monitoring products (cf. Isaksen et al. 2022) at <https://cryo.met.no/en/permafrost>.

2.2. 4.2.2 Borehole siting and configuration

4.2.2.1 *General principles, siting and aspect*

Borehole installation in remote cold regions and in high-mountain areas with steep and complex topography is costly and has challenging logistics. Site selection has therefore historically favored locations near communities, critical infrastructure and areas of specific research interests (S. L. Smith et al. 2022, Hock et al. 2019). Every location poses unique challenges and necessitates specific logistical arrangements. The evaluation and selection of a site should follow the general criteria outlined in Section 4.1.4. To define the exact drilling location at a selected site (i.e., where the drilling rig is placed), the criteria must again be considered for the specific location in view of the heterogeneity of the site characteristics and the rationale of the measurements (in this document the focus is on long-term observation in the context of climate change). The location of the drilling should be narrowed down by starting with coarse methods (like permafrost distribution maps) to geophysical site investigation to e.g., assess the ground ice distribution.

The local variations of the permafrost conditions include lateral variations in geothermal properties within the ground due to topography, snow cover, vegetation, surficial geology, ice content and bedrock type and fracturing. Glaciers, rivers and ocean, human encroachments (e.g., mines, roads, buildings, etc.) close to the chosen drill site can affect the thermal regime of the ground (Isaksen et al. 2000).

Surface and subsurface properties in cold regions can be heterogeneous, particularly in high mountain areas. A drilling site should therefore be representative for the general topographic setting (slope angle, solar radiation, snow accumulation). In addition, steep topography-induced lateral heat fluxes affect the subsurface temperature distribution (Noetzli and Gruber, 2009). When installing a borehole on a rock glacier, the horizontal annual surface deformation rate and its spatial distribution and the depth of the shear horizon must be considered before drilling (Noetzli et al. 2021). The latter is however often not known and can only be estimated.

Coastal and lower areas subject to isostatic uplift have been exposed to colder climate conditions for a shorter period of time. The ground may therefore still be cooling at depth and permafrost may still be forming depending on time since emergence.

4.2.2.2 *Borehole dimensions*

The minimal **depth** for temperature data to be included in the GTN-P database is generally defined to be the DZAA (Biskaborn et al., 2019), which is around 15–20 m for Alpine sites and 5–20 m for sites in Tundra areas, but may be less than 5 m at warm permafrost sites in the boreal forest. Often, a depth near DZAA and below is used for reporting long-term changes (see section 2.3.2) and to determine the temperature gradient with depth (e.g. Noetzli et al. 2021). However, reaching DZAA may not be possible due to subsurface material, available drilling equipment or difficulties of access with heavy equipment (e.g., remote areas or steep terrain). Continuous measurements of ground temperatures throughout the year (see Section 2.3) allow for the determination of long-term changes also for temperature measurements above the DZAA, e.g. at 10 m depth. Reaching the DZAA should therefore not be a limiting factor determining the usefulness of a borehole for long-term observations and the assessments of change rates. Deeper boreholes with several tens of meters depth – for example the 100 m deep PACE boreholes – allow inversion-modeling to assess the surface temperature evolution for several decades prior to drilling (e.g., Lachenbruch and Marshall, 1986; Isaksen et al., 2000).

The **diameter** of the borehole should be kept to a minimum to minimize effects of convective heat transfer in the borehole. It needs to be chosen wider for loose debris (ca. 100–140 mm) and can be smaller in solid bedrock and stable ground material (ca. 45–70 mm). In unconsolidated sediments, smaller diameter holes can also be made with e.g., some portable/hand augers and water jet drills (see Figure 4.2.2). The diameter is determined by the available equipment, the sampling technique and quality, drill bit and the selected casing. Also, the type of instrumentation to be installed in the borehole is relevant.

Boreholes can be drilled vertically to the surface or with a documented angular **orientation**. In unconsolidated material, as in loose debris or in sediments, it is recommended to seek a (nearly) vertical borehole angle, to minimize the risk of sidewall collapses. In steep bedrock terrain, surface normal or oblique boreholes may be installed to measure the permafrost temperature of rock faces (Magnin et al. 2015), or to investigate the complex temperature fields of steep crests and peaks (Gruber et al. 2004, Noetzli et al. 2008). Several boreholes

in the European Alps pierce a ridge completely to study thermal regimes and trends on two contrasting mountain sides (e.g., Noetzli et al. 2010; Phillips et al., 2016).

4.2.2.3 Borehole drilling

To establish boreholes in permafrost areas a variety of drilling methods exists (Figure 4.2.2). Selecting one depends on types of ground material (sediment, soil, bedrock etc.), topography and access, as well as the desired depth of the borehole, whether sampling will be done, and the budget. Drilling and sampling in remote permafrost areas are logistically and technically challenging, where budget and accessibility (and sometimes permitting requirements) probably are the major determining factors. It also requires specialized techniques, custom drilling equipment, knowledge and experience from the drillers and project coordinators (Christiansen et al., 2021; Noetzli et al., 2021). Weather conditions during drilling operations in cold environments are often demanding for both personnel and machines.

Figure 4.2.2. Different drilling techniques and settings in typical permafrost environments. a) Drilling of a new permafrost monitoring borehole on the north slope of the Schilthorn in the Bernese Alps (2950 m asl.) in Switzerland in September 2018. Photo: Cécile Pellet. b) Drilling with Talon system and adapted AMS frozen soil coring barrel to sample ice-rich morainal deposits, outer Mackenzie Delta, NWT, Canada in July 2022. Photo: Peter Morse. c) Drilling the 102 m deep PACE permafrost borehole on Janssonhaugen, Svalbard, in May 1998. Photo: Johan Ludvig Sollid. d) Operating a portable permafrost drilling system (SIPRE model) to retrieve permafrost cores from drained lake basins in Old Crow Flats, northern Yukon. Photo: Pascale Roy-Léveillé. e) Drilling of a new borehole in the frozen moraine at Gentianes in Switzerland in Summer 2022 to secure the 20 year permafrost temperature time series. Photo: Christophe Lambiel. Note that these are examples and the photos do not show all the potential drilling techniques or the settings they are shown in.

Drill types include augers (for unconsolidated material), portable water jet drills and a variety of rotary percussion drills (destructive drilling) and rotary core drills. While rotary percussion drilling is developed for advancing into the ground efficiently, the rotary core drills are intended for retrieving core samples (Christiansen et al., 2021). **Destructive drilling** may be less expensive, faster and require less planning depending on equipment used and if there are accessibility issues and high mobilization/demobilization costs. However, it only serves with qualitative information on stratigraphy, ice content, fractures, and water presence. Experienced surveillance of the ejectives is necessary to gain further insights into the material type and properties, as well as fissure and water presence (Phillips et al. 2023, Noetzli et al., 2021). For auger drilling, drill cuttings can be sampled and observed in the field. **Core drilling** is more expensive and time-consuming and can also be done for only a part of the borehole profile (and additionally requires a freezer or similar to store the frozen samples), but allows quantitative determination of stratigraphy, particle size and ice characteristics (geotechnical tests, dating, ground and ice composition). Duplex or triplex techniques should be used to minimize heat input into the ice core (Haeberli 1988; Vonder Mühl, 1996; Arenson et al., 2002) by drilling very slowly with compressor-driven air

in combination with air cooling or brine flushing system (no water). The drilling crown used depends on the type of drilling and on the ground material. In inhomogeneous terrain like a rock glacier, where rock and ice layers exist in close distance, fast adaptation of the drilling technique and crown may be needed (see Noetzli et al., 2021 for more details). Longer pauses during the drilling procedure should be avoided because the crown can become stuck due to freezing inside the borehole (after the drill rods have been warmed up by the drill process) and the borehole would be lost.

In remote Arctic areas, and far away from roads, drilling is typically conducted by the use of heli-portable drills or as rig transport during winter on frozen and snow-covered ground (Christiansen et al., 2021). Drilling during the winter also minimizes the impact of drilling on what will become a new long-term observation site. Even small disturbances to the arctic vegetation and landscape can lead to local deepening of the active layer, subsidence, ponding, and increased snow accumulation. In high mountain regions, drilling is typically conducted in spring or during summer. The drill rig and construction site installations must be transported by cable car, truck/bulldozer or helicopter. Road access is typically not possible. Depending on the local regulations, a building permit may be required.

To stabilize the drilling and to enable extraction or replacement of the installed instruments a **casing** is installed. This is particularly important for unconsolidated material and may not be necessary in bedrock. A borehole in loose debris needs to be supported by a casing immediately after drilling to prevent collapse and blocking (e.g. Arenson et al., 2002). The casing also protects the sensors and wires from damage and prevents adhesion of the sensors to the borehole walls. A material of low thermal conductivity, such as a round plastic (polyethylene) pipe (in accordance with PACE: Harris et al., 2001; Zhang, 2005) is preferred and no metal with high thermal conductivity should be used. However, a steel casing may for example be needed to protect the borehole from animal damage (bears or moose). The casing should have a diameter that suits the borehole and the inserted instruments. It should be sealed at the base and at all connections to be watertight. To limit potential for convection and improve conductive heat transport between the sensors and the ground, the space between the casing and the borehole wall can be filled with sand, environmentally safe fluid (e.g. silicone oil) or special permafrost-grout and larger cavities can be blocked with geotextiles (or other fabrics, see Noetzli et al., 2021). In a rock glacier,

however, the space will be filled with the deformation of the ground. To allow for additional (geophysical and calibration) measurements to be made in the future, a second tube can be inserted into the borehole (Boike et al., 2019).

A **covering** should be installed at the surface (e.g. metal box, plastic pipe or concrete chamber with iron lid), to protect the borehole and to reduce air convection (Streletskiy et al., 2022). The covering should hold space for additional material (e.g. sensor string suspension, data loggers, batteries) and include a water drainage. Keeping all devices close to the borehole reduces the cable length, which decreases the risk for damage due to lightning, measurement disturbances via heat conduction along the cables (Noetzli et al., 2021), damage due to animals (polar bear, foxes, rodents etc) and disturbances or damage due to heave and subsidence of the ground surface. Keeping logging equipment inside the casing protects it from the elements as well as from wildlife or tourists.

4.2.2.4 Borehole replacement

In some cases, it is no longer possible to access the sensors in the borehole for servicing or replacement because they cannot be removed from the borehole. Reasons for this can be borehole deformation, ice in the borehole due to water influx, a borehole filling material to stabilize the instruments, or the absence of a casing. When measurements become inconsistent or erroneous due to problems with the sensors in such a case, a replacement drilling may be needed to continue the time series (e.g., Noetzli et al., 2021; PERMOS, 2019). Boreholes reaching deeper than the shear horizon of a rock glacier may also need to be redrilled due to shearing off the cables and casing. The possible time of operation until cables shear off depends on the velocity of the rock glacier at the borehole location and at the depth of the shear horizon. For the homogenization of the time series measured in the old and new boreholes, it is important to guarantee a temporal overlap of the two systems (according to the GCOS Monitoring Principles (<https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/about/gcos-monitoring-principles>)).

2.3. 4.2.3 Continuous temperature measurements

4.2.3.1 *General principles*

Ground temperature monitoring sites typically consist of boreholes instrumented with permanently installed multi-sensor cables (so called temperature sensor strings) to continuously measure temperature at several depths using a logging system (S. L. Smith et al., 2022; Biskaborn et al., 2019; Noetzli et al., 2021; see Sections 4.2.3.2–4.2.3.4). Periodical retrieval of temperature sensor strings from the boreholes for maintenance (Section 4.2.3.7) and recalibration should be considered (Streletskiy, 2022; see Section 4.2.3.6), if possible. However, this is not possible in many cases (e.g. sensor string blocked in the borehole, logistically not possible in very remote places). In the latter case, inconsistencies such as sensor drift have to be checked for during data processing.

4.2.3.2 *Depth of measurement, sampling and recording interval*

Generally, the spacing of sensors on the temperature string should increase with depth due to the decreasing temporal variability in the ground temperatures. The requirements for sensor spacing depend on the subsurface characteristics and the thermal regime at the site (depth of the active layer, permafrost base, etc.), as well as the number of sensors available (e.g. by the logging equipment). Measurements at the **DZAA** were typically used for reporting in national and international assessments (e.g., Hock et al., 2019; Biskaborn et al., 2019)). With continuous recordings of ground temperature the DZAA is no longer considered a limiting factor of the usefulness of a borehole to determine long-term trends, and e.g. the depth of 10 m has been used for reporting (e.g. PERMOS 2023, Noetzli 2021). The recommended depths for permafrost temperature measurements defined by GTN-P are 5, 10, 20 m below the surface (Streletskiy et al., 2021), and the additional sensor placement defined based on the characteristics of the site, the borehole depth, and the used instrumentation. Where the risk for inaccessible/blocked temperature sensor strings is high, e.g. due to ice plugging or borehole shearing, temperature sensor duplication is essential to ensure uninterrupted time series at key depths (Noetzli et al., 2021; Widmer et al., 2023).

A spacing of 0.1–1.0 m is often applied in the uppermost 5–10 meters, and below around 10 m depth the spacing increases to 2–5 m down to around 30 meters. At larger depths, temperature is typically measured every 10 meters or more. However, depending on the site characteristics this spacing can vary. Specific depths may be defined to adapt to known

local characteristics, account for increasing active layer thickness and other known site-specific zones of interest, such as the DZAA, shear horizons, degrading permafrost, taliks or lateral water and air fluxes (Mühll and Holub, 1992; Arenson et al., 2002; Luethi and Phillips, 2016; Noetzli et al., 2021; Isaksen et al., 2022, Vonder Muehll and Haeberli 1990, Luo et al. 2018). Sensors should be duplicated at important depths (e.g. using different chains or very close distance) in case one gets damaged or exhibits drift (Noetzli et al. 2021). A closer spacing at the largest depth may help to validate deep temperatures. As an example, the regional PACE program has defined the following sensor spacing for a 100 m borehole has been defined as: 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 85, 90, 95, 97.5 and 100 m (Harris et al., 2001).

Measurements **near the surface** can be influenced by a protective borehole casing (e.g., concrete chamber changing the local snow cover and thermal regime) so a dense sensor spacing until 1 m depth may not be advisable. To prevent effects of a protective casing, an additional shallow borehole for precise temperature measurements can be installed in the proximity of the main borehole (e.g., PACE standard: 15–20 m depth, Harris et al., 2001; Isaksen et al., 2001). Alternatively, miniature temperature data loggers or fixed temperature sensors can be installed near the surface outside the borehole (e.g., Pogliotti et al., 2015; Isaksen et al., 2022; PERMOS 2019). Typically, measurement depths for single near-surface temperature sensors are at 0.05 m and 0.1 m depth, following the two standard uppermost depths for soil temperature measurements defined by WMO (WMO 2021). On rock glaciers and other coarse blocky ground material, the surface is difficult to define, such that measurements above about 1 m depth may become unreliable. In these cases, the definition of the surface level needs to be well justified and documented (Noetzli et al. 2021).

The **sampling and recording interval** depend mainly on the depth of the measurement, the purpose of the investigation and the type of instrumentation. Due to the higher temporal variability, the sampling interval in the uppermost meters must be set to a higher frequency, typically between 1h and 6h (Noetzli et al., 2021; Isaksen et al. 2022). Hourly sampling intervals can resolve variability in the uppermost meters, but may be limited by the required energy supply. Below the DZAA, a lower sampling rate with annual temperature measurements captures long-term trends. Below 50 m, measurements can be

repeated at a biennial rate, or less frequent, every 5 to 10 years . However, also at greater depths smaller sampling intervals may be helpful, since they allow to assess the measurement stability at depths with small temperature fluctuation as well as to capture potential non-conductive heat transport processes (Noetzli et al., 2021). Recording intervals are typically programmed for the entire sensor string and its definition is thus based on the minimum interval of interest. In addition, recording with high temporal resolution allows assessing the stability of the measurements at larger depths with small temperature fluctuations.

In areas with fine-grained soils and/or high ground ice content (including rock glaciers), **heave and subsidence of the ground surface** can complicate the fixed measurement depths as the level of the ground surface may vary through the year. For some sites long-term ground subsidence due to permafrost thaw requires careful attention regarding measurement depths and annual adjustments of the measurement's depth are essential to avoid misinterpretation of the measured temperature variations. Measuring distance between ground surface and e.g. top of the casing with a measuring tape during field visits is advisable as it will permit one to detect whether significant ground subsidence has occurred over time.

Especially at locations where the sensor string cannot be removed from the borehole for servicing (e.g. recalibration, see Section 4.2.3.6), sensor duplication is an very useful strategy for long-term monitoring to validate the measurements as well as for backup in case of erroneous sensors (e.g. drift, Widmer 2023, Noetzli 2021). Sensor duplication can be achieved by overlapping temperature sensor chains or by placing sensors with a minimal distance on the same sensor string. It is recommended to duplicate sensors at the key depths of 5, 10, and 20 m. Due to small-scale terrain heterogeneities it can be difficult to compare the data to nearby boreholes. The use of two different measurement systems can provide more security, since both systems will not be sensitive to the same perturbations, and may avoid simultaneous failure, as for example: a thermistor string and a digital temperature sensor string (Widmer et al. 2023) together with a sensor string and a fiber optic cable for DTS (Schoeneich et al. 2012, 2015).

4.2.3.3 *Temperature sensors*

Different types of temperature sensors and measurement systems are available to measure permafrost temperature in a borehole. The choice of the appropriate instrumentation depends on the specific measurement requirements, such as data accuracy and resolution, spatial and temporal resolution and coverage as well as installation and maintenance costs (e.g., Lundquist and Lott, 2008). For permafrost observations, the temperature sensors should have the highest absolute accuracy at 0 °C and cover the entire anticipated temperature range (Noetzli et al., 2021). A summary of the most often used types of temperature sensors is given below, but for an in-depth tutorial on temperature sensors, see Reverter (2021), for example.

Wires, contacts and casings of the sensor and logging systems (Section 4.2.3.4) should be equally hermetically sealed to prevent measurement disturbances due to moisture infiltration (Noetzli et al., 2021). To reduce convective heat transport after the installation of the instruments, the borehole can be filled with conducting fluid or, in case the sensor string remains permanently in the borehole, with sand. Insulation foam can also be added between the uppermost sensors, where the temperature gradient is the largest.

Resistance Temperature Sensors

For almost four decades, resistance temperature sensors have been the most used sensors in permafrost temperature studies. They operate based on the principle that the resistance of a material changes with changing temperature. That is, the temperature is calculated based on a well-known relationship between temperature and resistance. Based on the material the sensors are manufactured from, two different categories are generally distinguished, thermistors and resistance temperature detectors (RTDs).

Thermistors are generally manufactured from semiconductors and are characterized by a relatively high sensitivity and medium accuracy (Reverter 2021). Thermistors can either have a resistance that decreases with increasing temperature, called negative temperature coefficient (NTC), or a resistance that increases with increasing temperature, called positive temperature coefficient (PTC). The most commonly used in analog temperature sensor strings are NTCs, which are most typically manufactured from metal oxides. Measured

resistance is converted to temperature, often by the Steinhart–Hart equation, whose coefficients usually are published by thermistor manufacturers. The accuracy of a thermistor depends on the material and processes that were used for its production, the calibration and its coefficients and age, leading to a drift with time (e.g., Merlone et al., 2020). The age-dependent drift rate may correspond to <0.01 °C per year, depending on the manufacturer (Biskaborn et al., 2019). In addition, the relationship between resistance and temperature is non-linear for thermistors (or linear only for a small temperature window), leading to different accuracies for different temperature ranges. Typically, NTCs have a higher sensitivity at lower temperatures due to their characteristic line.

Resistance temperature detectors (**RTDs**) are manufactured from pure metals, commonly platinum (PRTD). RTDs operate on the principle that the resistance of a pure metal increases with increasing temperature (Reverter 2021). The accuracy of RTDs is higher than that of thermistors; however, their sensitivity is lower, often by several orders of magnitude. This lower sensitivity requires more sophisticated equipment to realize their higher accuracy and obtain the required resolution. Due to their high accuracy and linearity, PRTDs are often regarded as the industry standard for temperature sensing. Generally, measurement of thermistors or RTDs is performed by applying an excitation voltage and then measuring the voltage drop across the sensor. Thus, in sensor configurations with long cable lengths of several decameters, the resistance of the wires connecting the sensor to the measurement device can introduce significant errors. Due to the lower sensitivity of RTDs, they are more susceptible than thermistors to these measurement errors. To compensate for this, rather than measure the sensor in a common two-wire configuration, a four-wire configuration can be used (Reverter, 2021). However, this can be difficult to produce for long temperature sensor strings of several decameters in length. For analogue thermistor strings it is advisable to place a combination of thermistors on individual wires to prevent a loss of all sensors due to a single wire failure (Noetzli et al., 2021).

Silicon based digital temperature sensors

Silicon based digital temperature sensors are becoming increasingly popular, however, experience with long-term installations is still limited. These sensors can be incorporated into an integrated circuit (IC) so that the temperature sensor, measurement circuitry and

temperature conversion all take place on a single IC chip (Reverter, 2021). In this case, signal transmission inaccuracies are reduced by the digitization of the signal directly at the point of measurement. This system is less affected by moisture infiltration and lightning. However, digital sensors are typically mounted on one single cable, which increases the risk of total sensor failure in case of cable damage (Noetzli et al., 2021). Digital temperature strings have been tested in some permafrost boreholes. First analysis of temperatures measured by two sensor systems (thermistors and digital temperature sensors) under field conditions in mountain permafrost in Switzerland, at 15 identical depths in one borehole show that differences between the temperature sensor types are minimal, with less than 5% of all values outside of a 0.1 °C difference (Widmer et al. 2023). Experiences from five to ten years of monitoring with digital strings in Norway and Svalbard are also promising (Isaksen et al., 2022).

Thermocouples

Thermocouples are inexpensive, rugged and flexible temperature sensors (Osterkamp, 1985). Their working mechanism is based on temperature-dependent voltage that is produced at the junction of two dissimilar metals, known as the Seebeck effect (Reverter, 2021). They offer good resistance to weathering and corrosion. Since a thermocouple junction is also created at the point of connection to a measurement instrument, only the difference between the two junctions is measured. Thus, an accurate reference temperature (Thermistor or PRTD) is required. Their sensitivity and accuracy lie in between resistance thermometers and mechanical thermometers (Culik et al., 1982). Due to their relative low accuracy, they are no longer recommended for permafrost temperature monitoring applications today.

4.2.3.4 System configuration

Permanent installation of a temperature sensor string and connection to a data logger allows for a continuous record of ground temperatures at specific depths. Data loggers allow the measurement routine to be preset, to define the data format, to provide information on calibration, as well as conversion and data storage. In case of infrequent site visits and

depending on the sampling size and interval, loggers can save data for 1–2 years or more, assuming sufficient power is available. Remote access through a mobile network, satellite or radio communication allows for (near) real time data transmission as well as rapid intervention in case of potential technical problems (Isaksen et al. 2022, Noetzli et al. 2021). Logging systems can be protected inside the protective cover of the borehole or they can be fixed to a mast of a co-located weather station or solar panel.

The logging systems often use some combination of batteries, solar and/or wind for power, but also batteries alone are often used. In Arctic areas special care must be taken related to the dark season without solar power for several months. In mountain areas and lowland areas with thick snow cover, solar panels and wind turbines can be installed above the snow surface in avalanche-free locations to operate all year (wind turbines may be affected by freezing of their blades). In avalanche-affected terrain, safety is more important than solar-radiation reception (e.g. can be reduced by temporary snow coverage). Mounting the logging systems on a mast may protect them from (smaller) avalanches. In this case, the exposed box should be well ventilated to prevent inner condensation. Logging systems located at exposed high mountain sites need robust lightning protection that covers the entire observation installation (Noetzli et al., 2021): For this, the station should be only at one point connected to the ground and surface cable layout needs to be kept to a minimum. Cables can additionally be shielded, susceptible components insulated, and surge protection installed at the connection outlet of the logging box (Noetzli et al., 2021).

4.2.3.5 *Uncertainty and sources of error*

According to the International Vocabulary of Metrology (De Bièvre, 2012), **measurement accuracy** is defined as “closeness of agreement between a measured quantity value and a true quantity value of a measurand. [...] Accuracy is not a quantity and is not given a numerical quantity value”. The **uncertainty of a measurement**, on the other hand, must be associated with a non-negative number which “characterizes the dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used” and must be always evaluated when measurements are performed.

The **measurement uncertainty** of the entire measurement system is desired to remain at ± 0.1 °C or better according to the GTN-P measurement guidelines (Streletskiy et al., 2022). Breakthrough uncertainty is reached at ≤ 0.05 °C. The ideal measurement uncertainty is provided at ≤ 0.02 °C (cf. GCOS ECV Requirements) since the system uncertainty should be lower than the measured changes. Over one decade the permafrost temperature change below the DZAA can be in the order of a few decimal degrees Celsius (e.g., Biskaborn et al., 2019; Etzelmüller et al., 2020, S. L. Smith et al. 2022).

Not all sensors may easily fulfill the measurement uncertainty requirements over a larger temperature range, for example, an uncertainty of ± 0.1 °C from -30 °C to $+10$ °C (cf. Biskaborn et al. 2019, Noetzli et al. 2021, Streletskiy et al. 2022). Largest contributors to uncertainty depending on sensor type are potential drift, the hysteresis (ability to measure the same temperature starting from lower or higher temperature environments) and the sensitivity (see Section 4.2.3.3). In addition, measurements can be influenced by the configuration of the measurement system, which includes, for example, long cables, multiplexers etc.

The environment in which the sensors work can often be the largest source of uncertainty in measurements. Several associated quantities of influence can affect both the measurand and, more importantly, the sensors themselves. A further contributor to the measurement uncertainty in a permafrost setting, particularly for a shallow borehole, can be the degree of thermal contact between the sensor and soil: when a permafrost chain is put inside a borehole, in direct contact with the air inside the hole but not the soil around it, largest uncertainties arise given the low thermal conductivity of air itself and associated convective phenomena. Due to the low temperature gradient at large depth (< 0.1 °C m^{-1}) a mm-level positioning error has no effect on measurement accuracy (Biskaborn et al., 2019).

In boreholes subjected to borehole deformation, cable stretching may induce drift in recorded temperatures or breakage and destruction of the cable. In thermistors, the direction of drift depends on the influencing factor: they drift downwards (falsely low temperatures) if the wires are stretched (Luethi and Phillips 2016). Moisture infiltration

into the logging system, sensors or connections can induce an upward drift or (producing falsely high values, Luethi and Phillips 2016).

Ice often develops in the borehole tube at the level of the permafrost table, probably due to condensation of air moisture or damage to the tube. In some cases, it can evolve to form an ice plug that blocks melt water above it. This can affect measured temperatures, inducing a zero curtain which is not present in the surrounding ground. Ice plugs can be removed by melting them either with a heating device (electric resistance) or by blowing warm air (blow dryer). The effect of water infiltration and refreezing in the borehole on temperature measurements is almost unknown. Also, water may enter the borehole due to problems with the seal between casing sections (e.g. deterioration of the cement or improper application of cement).

Long-term permafrost monitoring in warm and/or saline permafrost will benefit from deeper boreholes to avoid the possibility of upward vertical displacement (frost jacking) of the casing. Casing pipes embedded insufficiently deep in permafrost may not have the resistance to counteract heaving forces developed in the active layer (cf. Ladanyi and Foriero, 1998, Gruber 2020).

4.2.3.6 Calibration

Traceability, i.e. “the property of a measurement result whereby the result can be related to a reference through a documented unbroken chain of calibrations, each contributing to the measurement uncertainty” (De Bièvre, 2012) is crucial to achieve comparable measurement results at different sites, with different systems, and in different times.

Sensor calibration may not be possible in all regions or settings or for all types of equipment. In most such cases sensors are either frozen in, blocked due to borehole deformation or the borehole was filled from the beginning. In remote Arctic locations it may logistically not be possible. On a rock glacier with borehole shearing, thermistors cannot be removed from the borehole after a few months/years, depending on the deformation rate and shearing of the borehole (cf. Noetzli et al. 2021). In addition, pulling out a sensor string

for recalibration bears the risk that it cannot be installed at the same depths or down to the bottom again.

Sensors should be provided with a calibration certificate from an accredited laboratory. For long-term monitoring the sensor drift of the temperature probe, e.g. for NTC thermistors, can lie in the range of the permafrost temperature trend to be captured. To ensure accurate measurements, instrument calibration becomes essential. Calibration is a documented comparison of the measurement system to be tested against a traceable reference standard. Calibration is typically performed in a **laboratory** prior to permanent field installation. Calibration of the sensors should be performed using the same instrument setup (i.e. temperature sensor string, logging device, cables, etc.) as is used at the measurement site. In the laboratory, sensors should be calibrated in a shaved ice-bath or snow-water bath controlled with an accurate reference thermometer (Wise, 1988). If the ice-bath is prepared properly and regularly stirred, it will be at 0 °C with an accuracy of at least 0.005 K. Also, a double bath (i.e. a bath in a bath) is sometimes used for better insulation to the outside temperatures. Further calibration points can also be performed using a liquid calibration bath and reference thermometer (Merlone et al. 2020).

Temperature calibration should involve at least three setpoints around 0 °C, to be able to interpolate (usually by means of a simple square polynomial) the behavior of the devices under test. To do this, an alcohol bath is required in which three temperatures can be set. In any case, the temperature range of the calibration should be larger than the actual temperature range experienced by the sensors during normal operation, because extrapolation introduces larger uncertainties than interpolation.

To achieve and maintain the prescribed system uncertainty, sensor **recalibration** should be performed every 5–10 years of station operation to identify sensor drift or after changes in the measurement setup. In reference sites or when low uncertainties are required (0.01 °C), re-calibration should be every 2–5 years, to correct for potential drift of used sensors and systems. Ideally sensor strings should be pulled out of the borehole for re-calibration in the laboratory. However, the remoteness of some boreholes does not allow for that. In such cases, calibration should be performed in the field. If a second access tube is installed in the borehole, it can provide an opportunity to control the plausibility of the data registered by the long-term sensors. One way to calibrate the sensors is to insert a high-precision,

calibrated PT1000 next to the long-term sensor. It is important to note that the equilibration time before the measurement can take several hours. There are systems, such as those described in Merlone et al. 2020, that can be brought to the measurement site and used for calibrating permafrost temperature sensors without the need for a complete disassembly of the system. These systems also have the advantage of allowing calibration in the same environmental conditions that the sensors and data logger system encounter during normal operation (temperature, wind, solar radiation, humidity, atmospheric pressure).

If the borehole setup is properly designed and established in a stable environment (e.g., in an air-filled casing without deformation of the borehole by permafrost creep), it may be possible to set up a second newly calibrated system in the same borehole and compare the measurements, ideally for a year, or as a minimum for one day to be sure that all sensors are allowed to come to equilibrium with the adjacent ground temperature.

4.2.3.7 Maintenance

Regular maintenance of the instruments is essential for a successful collection of continuous high-quality data, to repair or replace broken parts and to prolong the service life of the equipment (Noetzli et al., 2021). Maintenance typically includes one field visit per year, however, this may not be possible due to logistical or budget constraints (remoteness of the sites, number of boreholes to maintain). The maintenance should include visual control of all parts of the measurement system, i.e., logger box, batteries, modem and antenna, cables at the surface and their connections and protection and checks for possible subsidence or frost jacking of the borehole casing. It is also important to consider the replacement of certain components on a regular basis.

Regular field visits are particularly important if there is no remote access. In areas with many animals (mice, foxes, reindeer, bears, etc.) or that are prone to thunderstorms or natural hazards (avalanches, rock fall) that can potentially damage the installation, it is particularly important to look for damage and repair it. If possible, measures must be taken to prevent further damage in the future. Taking photographs of each part of the measurement system and the conditions at the site during each visit for the documentation of the current state (and hence any changes) has proven key for future reference. A

standardized field visit protocol helps with the full documentation of the station history including the work completed and changes or updates made to the instruments or logger program (Noetzli et al., 2021). Without such crucial information, later data processing, correction or homogenization is extremely difficult and time-consuming, or even impossible.

2.4. 4.2.4 Manual temperature reading

4.2.4.1 *General principles*

Logging of boreholes by lowering a single sensor probe (Figure 4.2.3) is still common, especially for boreholes deeper than 40 m in Arctic areas (Osterkamp 2003 and S. L. Smith et al. 2010, 2022). To allow for permafrost temperature data comparison, repeated measurements should be taken in the same spatial and temporal frame when possible (same measurement depth and time of the year). Further, the time stamp should be shared along with the data, indicating if the measurement has been taken at one single time, or if it reflects the average value of a time period. (As in GTN-P:

<https://gtnp.arcticportal.org/data/data-handling/19-data/mining/80-protocols-good-work-practices>)

Figure 4.2.3. (left) Borehole at Galbraith Lake, Alaska with manual measurement system in place (photo: William Cable). The system consists of a measurement tape on a reel with a self-contained temperature logger mounted to the end. (right) Thirty years of annually measured borehole temperature data from Galbraith Lake (Romanovsky et al. 2022 and Osterkamp 2003). The borehole was drilled in 1985 and is 75 m deep.

While it is generally undesirable to take measurements only once per year from a borehole, one advantage is that the same, well calibrated, sensor is used at all depths and in all boreholes. Thus, quality and confidence in the measurements can be higher than that of temperature string-based measurements. Therefore, boreholes allowing manual measurements are an excellent way to check an installed temperature chain for drift (cf.

Section 4.2.3.6). In addition, annual measurements at depths below the ZAA are considered sufficient to capture the long-term changes of the permafrost temperature driven by a conductive thermal regime.

4.2.4.2 *Depth of measurement, sampling and recording interval*

Generally, the depth of measurements is the same as with measurements using temperature sensor strings (Section 4.2.3). Sampling of the borehole temperature profile is performed by lowering a temperature sensor step-wise into the borehole, pausing at each depth of interest to allow the sensor to adequately equilibrate. Here it is helpful if the sensor cable is marked with depth to allow accurate placement of the sensor.

Typically, the upper 10 to 15 m are measured with 1 m spacing and the deeper depths at 2 or 5 m spacing, depending on available time and if the borehole is liquid or air filled. The borehole filling (liquid or air), the temperature gradient between measurements, and the thermal mass of the sensor determine the amount of time required for the sensor to equilibrate (Widmer et al. 2023). For example, in a liquid filled borehole this time may be as short as 2 or 3 minutes, whereas in an air filled borehole equilibration may take up to an hour or more. Thus, it is important to test a sensor's equilibration time in the borehole medium before use. The recording interval should be set so that it can be clearly observed when and if the sensor has equilibrated.

4.2.4.3 *Temperature sensors*

The measurement systems currently in use generally provide an accuracy and precision of 0.1 °C or better and are either based on resistance temperature (cf. Section 4.2.3.3.1) or digital temperature (cf. Section 4.2.3.3.2) techniques.

4.2.4.4 *System configuration*

A typical manual temperature system consists of the temperature sensor and measuring device. Often this is a temperature sensor (thermistor), attached by a long cable to either a data logger or resistance meter (Osterkamp 2003). Care should be taken with long cable

lengths as the resistance of the cable itself starts to become a factor and needs to be compensated for (e.g. 3 or 4-wire bridge). The use of a digital temperature sensor eliminates this problem because the temperature conversion is performed at the sensor and transmitted as a digital signal. With the measuring device at the surface the temperature or resistance can be monitored until the sensor value is no longer changing, the sensor is in equilibrium.

Another possible system configuration is to have the sensor and data logger combined into one device that is lowered into the borehole. While this is a simple and effective measurement technique, the user is “flying blind” and will have to wait at each depth a predetermined amount of time for the sensor to equilibrate.

Sometimes, permanently installed multisensor temperature cables are not connected to a continuous logging system for logistical or other reasons. In this case, measurement of these cables requires a high accuracy digital multimeter.

4.2.4.5 Uncertainty and sources of error

The sources of error and uncertainty are generally the same as with temperature strings (cf. Section 4.2.3.5), with the exception of sensor drift as the sensor can be calibrated before and after every use.

4.2.4.6 Calibration

Generally, sensor calibration is the same as with temperature strings (cf. Section 4.2.3.6). Before each measurement campaign, the sensor and measurement system should be calibrated or at a minimum, checked in an ice-bath.

4.2.4.7 Maintenance

Temperature sensors and measurement systems should be kept in good working order to ensure the quality of the data. Temperature sensors should be replaced when drift becomes excessive and can no longer be compensated for through calibration.

2.5. 4.2.5 Fiber optic (Distributed Temperature Sensing)

Distributed Temperature Sensors (DTS) are optoelectronic devices that can measure temperature via optical fibers. In contrast to conventional point-sensor methods, DTS sensors provide high spatial and temporal resolution, by recording continuous temperature measurements along a cable that defines the profile (Tyler et al., 2009). Measurements are based on the detection of back-scattered light pulses. For high temperature precision, Raman back-scattering is used. Modern instruments allow a spatial resolution of 0.5 or even 0.25 cm along the fiber optic cable, on cable lengths up to several km (Ukil et al., 2012). The new technology has been applied to some few sites in polar (e.g. Roger et al., 2015) and mountain permafrost (e.g. Schoeneich et al., 2015, Harrington and Hayashi, 2019) environments. It has been used in boreholes as well as for spatial monitoring of subsurface evolution (Roger et al., 2015) and has proven to effectively capture thermal transfer processes. Technical specification as well as an example of a borehole installation can be found in Schoeneich et al. (2012). Further studies need to evaluate if long-term implementation of fiber optic cables is feasible in the dynamic environment of permafrost, where frost processes cause ground perturbation and cracking (Roger et al., 2015).

4.2.5.1 System configuration

DTS is measured along a fixed fiber optic cable (coated quartz fiber), that can be either laid down in a subsurface trench (Roger et al., 2015) or installed in a borehole (Schoeneich et al. 2012). The cable must be longer than the measurement section, the remaining length at the beginning and the end of the cable being used for calibration. The fiber cable should be accessible from both ends, in order to allow a double ended measurement.

DTS can be measured either periodically, or monitored continuously. The measurement instrument is however very expensive and in the very harsh conditions common in permafrost areas, the instrument must be protected for continuous measurements.

4.2.5.2 Calibration

DTS measurement gives relative values that need to be calibrated. Modern instruments include an internal calibration, but for periodic measurements it is necessary to calibrate the device every time in an ice/water bath.

4.2.5.3 *Uncertainty and sources of errors*

Theoretical accuracy of DTS measurements are given at less than 0.1 °C, or even 0.01 °C. This can however be reached only with long measurement times. In case of periodic measurements with short measurement times (1-2 hours), the observed uncertainty is in the range of 0.1 °C. This can be reduced by calculating average values on double ended or replicated fiber sections or measurements. The calibrated uncertainty has to be added to the measurement uncertainty, so that the total uncertainty can be estimated to be in the order of +- 0.1 °C (Schoeneich et al. 2015).

2.6. 4.2.6 Subsea permafrost temperature measurements

Measurements of subsea permafrost can be available from borehole logs acquired in offshore wells (e.g. for oil and gas exploration). The borehole measurement locations often depend on the locations of hydrocarbon fields. Further, hydrocarbon boreholes are typically designed for depths significantly exceeding permafrost thickness, which requires a larger borehole casing diameter in the uppermost sediment section, which can affect the quality of temperature measurements. Underwater drilling is very challenging and expensive. If possible, alternative drill sites may be placed at or near offshore islands (Ruppel et al., 2016). With distance from the shore, subsea permafrost evolves from continuous to discontinuous permafrost.

Currently subsea permafrost temperature determination relies mainly on bottom water temperature measurements and sediment temperature probes that can constrain the upper boundary conditions for heat flux modeling in subsea sediments (Nicolosky et al., 2012; Frederick and Buffett, 2015; Gavrillov et al., 2020). In this case, borehole temperature measurements may be used. However, those are typically compromised by seawater, drilling fluids and hole conditions and have to be analyzed with extra caution. In shallow water, to prevent sea water from entering the borehole, a metal casing can be drilled into the seafloor sediments through the sea ice water column. For example, an approach has been described by Overduin et al. (2016), using a portable rotary drill rig and a dry drilling technique.

3. 4.3 MEASUREMENTS OF ACTIVE LAYER THICKNESS

3.1. 4.3.1 General

This Section describes the most common methods of direct in situ thaw depth measurements used for assessing the active layer thickness (ALT) in permafrost-affected environments, its spatial variability, and temporal dynamics. The provided information is for direct active layer measurements using end-of-season manual probing and a visual interpretation of the active layer thickness using a thaw depth indicator gauge (frost or thaw tube). The active layer thickness can also be estimated using a vertical profile of temperature sensors extending through the active layer and upper permafrost. The measurement strategy, as well as the pros and cons will be presented for each technique.

4.3.1.1 Definitions

The term 'active layer thickness' (ALT) in permafrost-affected regions refers to the thickness of the thawed layer (measured relative to the ground surface) that is reached at the end of the warm season (van Everdingen, 1998). The term 'thawed' can indicate either melting of ice or warming above 0 °C. The distinction between temperature-based and phase transition-based definitions is relevant as the ice-nucleation temperature in soils can be depressed due to salinity, capillary effects, and pressure, causing the ground to remain unfrozen at temperatures below 0 °C. As a result, the bottom portion of the active layer defined on the basis of phase changes of water can be considered as a part of the permafrost layer. The ALT is distinct from the term 'thaw depth,' which refers to the thickness of the thawed layer at any time during its development. In permafrost environments, the maximum annual thaw depth is indicative of the annual thickness of the active layer. In other words, thaw depth is essentially an instantaneous value that is always less than or equal to the thickness of the fully developed active layer. The thickness of the active layer is inferred from the thaw depth measurements at the end of the thawing season.

Unless otherwise specified, a thaw depth measurement refers to a measurement at a single location at a given time and a thaw depth survey is a series of measurements at a single site following a predetermined spatial pattern. Thaw depth is typically measured in cm.

4.3.1.2 Spatial and Temporal Variability of the Active layer thickness

Factors influencing thaw depth and thickness of the active layer and their spatial and temporal distribution include: 1) mean annual ground surface temperature; 2) the amplitude of the annual temperature cycle at the ground surface; 3) the composition and thermal properties of the surface cover and subsurface material, and 4) the ground moisture regime. Zonal trends in ALT are discernable if similar soils and surface cover are considered at all sample locations (Luo et al., 2016). In general, ALT decreases poleward and with elevation, and increases in continental areas with lower elevations. At local and regional scales, however, both thaw depth and the active layer thickness are highly variable over space in response to variations in subsurface properties, soil moisture, topographic position, and snow and surface cover (vegetation, debris, etc.). The spatial variability of thaw depth tends to increase over the course of a single warm season due to variable rates of thaw propagations through surface and subsurface materials with highly heterogeneous properties (Hinkel and Nelson, 2003). Due to the high variability of ALT over short lateral distances, thaw depth surveys are preferable for generating samples statistically representative of local conditions (cf. Section 4.4.1.3).

Active layer thickness can vary substantially on an interannual basis in response to variability in atmospheric climate (e.g., air temperature, precipitation).

3.2. 4.3.2 Active layer thickness observations

Observations of the active layer thickness involve direct measurements of the end-of-season thaw depth during one or more years. There are two primary ways in which this is accomplished:

- 1) Measurements aimed at the identification of the maximum annual depth to frozen (ice-bonded) Earth material by manual probing (Section 4.3.4). Manual probing observations may consist of a measurement at a single point or thaw depth surveys with multiple measurements in a predetermined spatial pattern (e.g., transects, grids). Unlike a point measurement, the observation of thaw depth surveys enables the observer to assess the spatial variability at the observation site (Brown et. al., 2000) (Figure 4.3.1). Manual thaw depth probing at the end of the thawing season is the most frequently used method to monitor ac-

tive layer changes at the Circumpolar Active Layer Monitoring (CALM) network of observational sites (e.g. Nelson et al., 2021) which has led to numerous long-term studies (e.g. Abramov et al., 2021; Kaverin et al., 2021; Nyland et.al., 2021; Oblogov et al., 2023; Strand et.al., 2021).

Figure 4.3.1. (A) Thaw depth measurements by mechanical probing conducted at the Circumpolar Active Layer Monitoring (CALM) Site in Arctic Alaska. (B) A landform map of CALM U1 (Utqiagvik) 1 km x 1 km site. The site encompasses major landforms characteristic of the North Slope of Alaska. Locations of 121 annual thaw depth measurements are indicated by intersections of dashed grid lines and (C) Spatial representation of 1995-2023 mean of the annual end-of-thaw season (third week of August) thaw depth measurements from the CALM U1 (Utqiagvik) 1 km x 1 km site.

- 1) Visual interpretation of the maximum annual depth of the 0 °C isotherm propagation using a thaw depth indicator gauge (frost or thaw tube)(Bonnaventure and Lamoureux, 2013; Mackay 1973) (Section 4.3.5). Thaw/frost tubes are devices extending from above the ground surface through the active layer and anchored in the underlying permafrost (Figure 4.3.2). They are used to derive active layer thickness value for the preceding summer independent of the vertical position of the ground surface and corrected to a standard height above the ground established during installation (i.e., a fixed datum). Examples of frost

tube applications for active layer monitoring can be found in Christiansen (2004); Garibaldi et.al., 2022; Mackay 1973; O’Neill et.al., (2023, 2019); Smith & Brown, (2009); Vieira et.al., (2010).

Figure 4.3.2. A) Schematic diagram of the typical thaw tube used to measure the active layer thickness (ALT) and ground surface (GS) elevation (after Mackay, 1973). B) Thaw tube installed at the Reindeer Depot (C07) CALM site in the Northwest Territories, Canada. C) A long-term ground surface elevation, and active layer thickness record from 28 thaw tube sites in North-West Canada. The values are plotted relative to the first year's value in the record for each site. (after O’Neill et.al., 2023). With permission from Natural Resources Canada.

As previously noted, these two measurement strategies may yield different results, representing an example of the problems arising from differing active layer definitions.

3.3. 4.3.3 Site Selection

Prior knowledge of the surface and subsurface conditions of the area should guide the appropriate site selection (see also Section 4.1.4). Specifically, it should be considered that manual probing works best in organic and fine-grained subsurface materials that are ice-bonded when frozen. However, probing is not a useful method for determining thaw depths in areas with very thick active layers (approximately >2 m as typically measured in mid-latitude mountain areas), areas containing consolidated Earth material (bedrock), or areas where the surface is covered in coarse debris (rock glaciers, talus). Well-drained sands and gravels may contain too little interstitial ice for adequate resistance to probing to develop. Accurate readings may be very difficult to obtain in stony substrates such as glacial till. As a result, simple probing may not be suitable in mountainous areas or areas with a complex topography and surface/subsurface conditions where active layer thicknesses can vary considerably, or permafrost can go from being present to absent over short horizontal or vertical distances. For these areas, the ALT can only be determined based on the 0 °C isotherm (see Section 4.3.6).

Because in many cases measurements can be made rapidly and with little effort, probing is well-suited for implementing thaw depth surveys to obtain a statistical sample of active layer thickness values representative of local surface and subsurface conditions. The ideal site for probing surveys should be representative of the surrounding landscapes usually identifiable based on topography (e.g. slope, exposition, concavity/convexity) and ground surface cover (e.g. vegetation, surface water) (see Section 4.1.4). Ideally, each site should encompass the local-scale variability in microtopographic features of the landscape. Examples of typical microtopographic variability within permafrost-affected landscapes may include tundra polygons, hummocks or tussocks, frost mounds/palsas, water-filled depressions, and small water tracks (Boike et.al., 2022).

The typical site for thaw depth surveys consists of a series of regularly spaced observational nodes arranged along transect(s) or in a grid pattern across/within the representative landscape (Brown et. al., 2000). The size of the grid and the length of the transects can vary depending on site geometry, the scale of the active layer's local variability, and monitoring objectives. Transects are typically 10 to 100 m in length with sampling nodes spaced 1 to 10 m apart. Grids range between 10, 100, and 1000 m on a side, with nodes distributed

evenly at 1, 10, or 100 m spacing, respectively (Figure 4.3.1). An exploratory sampling may be necessary to establish transects or grids of dimensions appropriate to the local conditions and the scientific goals. In many instances, it is more advantageous to establish a site consisting of several shorter/smaller transects/grids representing major relatively homogeneous landscape units characteristic of the area than trying to capture all local variability with one long/large transect/grid. To facilitate interannual comparison, sampling node locations along a transect or within a grid are identified using stakes or other semi-permanent markers, and replicate measurements are made at approximately the same location each year.

Frost/thaw tubes can be installed in areas where thaw propagation is too deep to monitor by probing, and in stony, fine-textured, or saline substrates in which probing is not feasible. An important advantage of thaw tubes over probing is the ability to capture the maximum thaw depth. However, unlike manual probing, each frost/thaw tube record consists of only a single-point measurement which might not be representative of the surrounding landscape. As a result, the exact location of a single frost tube should be determined based on an extensive thaw depth probing survey at the end of the first summer of measurements. The gauge installation point should be representative of the mean end-of-season thaw depth for the entire landscape. If logistically possible, periodic probing surveys timed to coincide with maximum thaw depth are recommended to assess the spatial representativeness of the point measurement (Tarnocai et.al., 2004).

Manual probing does not produce any negative environmental impact other than that caused by walking. For sites intended for long-term monitoring, the issue of surface disturbance must be therefore considered. Periodic walking along the same path can in some instances disturb the natural vegetation cover altering the ground thermal regime and affecting thaw depth. Logistical constraints such as accessibility should also be considered when establishing long-term monitoring sites. Frost/thaw tube installation typically involves drilling which might result in significant disturbance of the surface and subsurface materials.

The characteristics of the observational site should be captured in the site metadata. Important site details for thaw depth measurements to be listed in the metadata include, but may not be limited to, location (GPS coordinates), general climate and permafrost characteristics, slope, aspect, surface and subsurface parameters (vegetation type/height,

surface hydrology, organic and/or subsurface layers, ground ice, etc.) of the location, site layout and sampling strategy.

3.4. 4.3.4 Manual thaw depth probing

4.3.4.1 Probing Equipment

The standard tool to measure thaw depth by manual probing is a metal rod with a handle called a probe. Other common names include 'frost probe,' 'ALT probe,' 'tile probe,' and 'active layer probe.' The typical probe is a 1 m to 1.3 m long metallic rod with a tapered point and is 1 cm in diameter (Figure 4.3.2.1 A). The simplest probe is a sharpened metallic rod welded to a pipe. Because the probe will remain continually wet in the saturated soils a stainless steel rod should be used to prevent rusting. Graduated probes have distances in cm engraved onto the rod to simplify measuring. Breakdown probes come apart for easy shipping, with the pieces stored in the handle. At sites where the thaw depth is large (e.g., 1–3 m) longer probes should be used. The diameter of the long probe must also be greater to withstand the bending stress generated by insertion. However, it should be considered that it is very difficult to extract a probe in deeply thawed soils if the probe's surface area is very large.

4.3.4.2 Timing

Timing of the thaw depth probing is essential for determining the thickness of the active layer. Ideally, measurements should be collected at the time of maximum thaw penetration which can vary from year to year and with a location. Ground temperature monitoring within the active layer and near-surface permafrost can also be used to estimate the timing of the maximum depth of thaw penetration. However, the exact date when the thaw depth reaches its annual maximum at a specific site is impossible to predict. Moreover, field measurements are often constrained by logistical or weather-related considerations. It is therefore unlikely that the measurement of thaw depth coincides perfectly with the actual active layer thickness. The Circumpolar Active Layer Monitoring (CALM) component of the Global Terrestrial Network- Permafrost (GTN-P) addresses this problem by conducting annual thaw depth measurements during the same calendar week at the end of the thawing season (mid-August to mid-September in the Northern Hemisphere) (Luo et al., 2014;

Nelson et.al.,2021; Nyland et.al., 2021). While this approach provides only the approximate thickness of the active layer in any given year, it ensures consistency of the thaw depth record for discerning long-term trends.

4.3.4.3 Measurement Procedure

Manual probing to measure thaw depth is a simple procedure. The observer pushes the probe into the ground normally to the surface until it encounters a resistance by the ice-bonded layer which is also indicated by a distinct “thump” sound. Once the frozen layer is reached, the observer places the thumb at the surface and pulls the probe out of the ground. The penetration depth of the rod is then measured from the pointed end of the rod to the observer’s thumb using a measuring tape, or from graduated marks on the rod. Observations are conducted in cm and are rounded to the nearest centimeter.

Probes typically cannot penetrate the rocky ground or tree roots and make a ‘ping’ or scraping sound when encountering stones/roots, rather than a ‘thump’ when hitting the frozen ground. If a stone is encountered the measurement should be tried in a different nearby spot. If it is impossible to find a spot without rocks at a specific sampling node, this is noted in the data log.

When observations are conducted in barens or areas covered with grass or woody shrubs, the observer’s thumb is pushed down to the soil surface. When probing in moss- or lichen-covered areas where the vegetation-soil boundary is hard to define the observer’s thumb is pushed down to depress vegetation until resistance. When probing in standing water, both thaw depth and water depth are recorded. On inclined surfaces, the probe should be inserted perpendicular to the ground.

During a thaw depth survey, typically two measurements are performed within one meter of the node marker and each other at each sampling node, and the average of two measurements is reported.

4.3.4.4 Uncertainty and sources of error

The major sources of error associated with the manual thaw depth probing include the observer's errors when reading or recording the measurement, or interpreting the location of the ice-bound frozen layer relative to the surface.

Errors in manual measurements may result from misinterpretation of a thaw depth reading or incorrect entry in a log book. These can be minimized by following measurement procedures. With due care and observer experience, many of these sources of error can be minimized. Errors in measurements of this type can usually be removed through data quality control processes.

Significant uncertainty can result from determining the location of the ground surface in vegetated or water-covered areas. For example, vegetation like moss or lichen has spatially varying levels of compression during thumb placement or it might be difficult to correctly locate the ground surface in standing water. This can be especially relevant for hummocky/tussocky terrain where the observed thaw depth can be significantly different depending on whether the measurement is taken on top or at the base of the hummock/tussock. Similarly, the observer can misinterpret the location of the ice-bonded frozen layer in areas underlain by a stony substrate. These errors can be avoided by having prior knowledge of the surface and subsurface conditions and through the observer's experience. The magnitude of such errors, depending on vegetation and edaphic properties could range from a few centimeters to tens of centimeters. The accuracy of a single thaw depth measurement by manual probing in moss-covered tundra underlain by fine-grained subsurface material with a well-defined thawed/frozen interface is estimated at ± 2 cm. Rounding off to the nearest centimeter introduces an uncertainty of about ± 0.5 cm.

A primary concern for the accuracy of long-term active layer thickness assessments using thaw depth observations is the potential inconsistency of the probing measurements from year to year. A discrepancy in annual end-of-season thaw depth value may result from inconsistent timing of the observations and inconsistent selection of probing location(s) in sites with complex microtopography. In addition, if measurements are conducted by different observers the amount of pressure exerted by each individual during probing might not be consistent. Another concern is related to the potential for site disturbance and year-to-year ground surface subsidence which is possible in environments with high ground-ice

contents (e.g., Shiklomanov et al., 2013). Subsidence is a phenomenon that occurs when the ground surface sinks or settles due to the removal of underlying material, such as the melting of subsurface ice in permafrost areas. Surface subsidence is important because even if measurements are taken by the same observer(s) in successive years, changes in thaw depth derived from manual probing might not be detected or underestimated, as lowering of the permafrost table is accompanied by subsidence of the ground surface (Brendan et al. 2019). As a result, thaw depth observations collected to detect interannual variability of the active layer thickness should be as consistent as possible. The use of secondary measurements (e.g. thaw tubes, ground temperature monitoring) can potentially minimize the uncertainty related to a year-to-year inconsistency in manual thaw depth probing (Bonnaventure and Lamoureux, 2013). In some situations, long-term changes in active layer thickness obtained by mechanical probing without consideration for surface movement can underestimate the total response of ice-rich permafrost to climatic forcing (O'Neill et al., 2023; Shiklomanov et al., 2013; S. L. Smith et al. 2022).

3.5. 4.3.5 Frost/thaw tubes gauges

4.3.5.1 Measurement device

Frost/thaw tubes represent a gauge that allows an observer to evaluate the active layer thickness by visually determining the maximum depth of 0 °C isotherm propagation in any given year. Several variants of frost/thaw tubes which differ by construction material and design are available (e.g. Christiansen, 2004; Mackay, 1973; O'Neill et al., 2023; Rickard and Brown, 1972; Smith and Brown, 2009; Tarnocai et al., 2004; Vieira et al., 2010, Sharratt and McCool, 2005). The typical gauge consists of nested plastic tubes. A rigid outer tube is made of plastic (PVC) with a watertight plug at the bottom and a removable watertight screw cap on top. It is anchored into the permafrost to a depth well below the active layer. A flexible transparent inner tube extends below the potential maximum thaw depth for the area and contains liquid water (Figure 4.3.2.2). Once placed within the ground, the water will freeze at the 0 °C isotherm indicating the position of the frost table. In order to determine the active layer thickness indicated by maximum thaw propagations in a given season, a small marker is dropped into the inner tube and rests on the top of the water/ice interface. As thaw propagates downward the marker follows the water-ice

interface until maximum depth is reached. On refreezing, it is incorporated into the ice and records the maximum annual thaw depth or active layer thickness for that year. If sufficiently anchored in the permafrost, frost/thaw tubes can also be used to measure ground surface heave and/or subsidence by installing a scribe that is allowed to move vertically, positioned level with the ground surface, and encircling the immobile outer tube (Tarnocai et al., 2004). The position of the scribe will provide information on the vertical position of the ground surface by recording maximum (frost heave) and minimum (thaw subsidence) surface elevations achieved during the year. To provide the total thaw penetration, active layer thickness values can be corrected to account for net ground surface deformation.

4.3.5.2 *Installation and Measurement Procedure*

The initial installation of thaw tubes should be done in the winter or at the beginning of the thaw season in order to ensure that the marker rests on top of the water/ice interface before maximum thaw penetration. The outer tube is installed into a predrilled hole filled with slurry and allowed to freeze in place. To prevent frost heave, the outer tube should be long enough to be anchored in permafrost. Anti-heave rings can be firmly attached to the outer tube to prevent frost heaving. The uppermost ring should be located well below the potential active layer. Within the active layer, the space around the outer tube should be filled with sand to minimize soil adhesion to the tube and to provide better thermal contact between the tube and the ground. The diameter of the outer tube should be relatively small to prevent unnecessary site disturbance (Mackay, 1973; Nixon and Taylor, 1994; Tarnocai et al., 2004; Sharratt and McCool, 2005)

A removable, water-filled, clear plastic observation tube should withstand expansion when water freezes. The inner tube should be long enough to extend well below the potential active layer of the area and have a diameter that allows ample play between two tubes to prevent binding when frozen. A 2.5m long, 2 cm in diameter inner tube placed inside a 2.5 cm diameter, 4m long outer tube should work well for most permafrost-affected landscapes.

The thaw depth marker should be placed in the inner tube after the water in the tube freezes to the frost table of adjacent ground. The marker should be placed before the thaw

depth reaches its annual maximum (winter or early summer). Freezing is rapid if installation is done in winter. In summer the ice surface in the inner tube can lie below the ground frost line since a large amount of heat needs to be removed to freeze the water. The size and density of the marker should be such to resist vertical movement with a freezing front. Field and laboratory experiments indicate that a colored glass bead 3 mm in diameter works very well (Nixon et.al., 1995).

If the thaw tube is equipped with a heave/subsidence gauge, the scribe of the gauge is placed level with the ground surface and a reference mark is made on the outer tube to indicate the position of the scribe. Maximum frost heave and subsidence are recorded by a scribe scratching a painted surface of the outer tube on either side of a reference mark (Nixon and Taylor, 1994; O'Neill et. al., 2023; Tarnocai et al., 2004)

The active layer thickness observations are conducted after the thaw depth for the year of interest reached its annual maximum. Usually, before the maximum thaw of the following summer. At that time, the inner tube is raised and the vertical position (depth) of the bead is measured in cm relative to the stable reference point represented by the outer tube. To ensure that the expansion of the water column during freezing is only upward, the bottom of the inner tube is examined. The maximum surface heave and subsidence are observed by measuring the length of scratches above (for heave) and below (for subsidence) the reference mark on the outer tube which represents a fixed datum.

The maximum thaw penetration, which is assumed to occur at the time of maximum ALT is calculated as the depth of the bead minus the height of the ground surface at maximum surface subsidence (Nixon et.al., 1995; Tarnocai et al., 2004). The values of active layer thickness, heave/subsidence, and thaw penetration are reported in cm and are rounded to the nearest centimeter.

After observations are complete, a bead of different color is introduced to the inner tube, and the paint and a surface reference mark on the outer tube are renewed.

4.3.5.3 *Uncertainty and sources of error*

Since the active layer observations using frost/thaw tubes involve manual measuring of distance/length, the observer's mistakes can result in erroneous observations. As with any manual measurements, this type of error can be minimized by the diligence and experience of the observer.

The principal errors in frost/thaw tube measurements come from heat conduction down the tube during the summer resulting in an overestimation of the observed thaw depth and active layer thickness. This error tends to be larger at the beginning of the thawing season and then decreases along with the increase in thaw depth. Field research conducted in continuous permafrost regions of Canada indicates that the overall accuracy of measurements using frost/thaw tubes are within 5% of the thaw depth (Mackay, 1973). To minimize the error, the outer tube should be made of light-colored low-heat conductive material and protrude only slightly above the ground surface. If possible, installation should be done in shaded areas.

The inner tube with an ice column containing a bead can experience expansion and contraction due to extremes of near-surface ground temperature. In properly constructed and installed gauges this error is less than 0.01cm (Nixon et al., 1995). However, a detailed study conducted in the seasonal frost areas of Japan indicated that the accuracy of frost/thaw tubes in determining the depth of frost/thaw penetration is ± 0.035 m (Iwata et.al., 2012).

The largest errors can potentially result from improper installation of the frost/thaw tubes. For example, not adequately anchoring of the outer tube in permafrost can result in its vertical movement due to frost heave and/or thaw subsidence resulting in erroneous or inconsistent thaw depth and active layer thickness values. However, periodically (yearly) measuring the height of the outer pipe above the ground surface allows this error to be accounted for.

To evaluate frost/thaw tube performance it is recommended to conduct thaw depth probing in multiple locations in close proximity to the gauge during each site visit. For a properly working gauge, the depth of the ice/water interface in the inner tube should be within the range of thaw depth values obtained by probing.

The overall accuracy of a properly installed and maintained thaw tube is ~ 2 cm (Smith and Brown 2009).

3.6. 4.3.6 Inferring active layer thickness from the ground temperature measurements.

The active layer thickness can be inferred from the maximum annual propagation of the 0°C isotherm into the ground estimated from the temperature records obtained by a vertical array of temperature sensors inserted or installed in a borehole or a soil profile (e.g., Hrbáček et al., 2021, Noetzli et al. 2021, Haberkorn et al. 2021, Isaksen et al. 2022, see Section 4.2.3). Usually, the thickness of the active layer is estimated by locating the maximum annual depth of the 0°C isotherm by linearly interpolating between the lowermost thermistor in the active layer (where the maximum annual temperature is positive) and the uppermost thermistor in the permafrost (where the maximum annual temperature is negative). The exponential best-fit interpolation can also be employed if there are several thermistors. The installation procedure, monitoring equipment, calibration, and accuracy are similar to those described in sections related to measurements of permafrost temperature using thermistor strings (see Section 4.2.3). However, to achieve higher accuracy of the active layer estimates the sensor spacing should be reduced to 2-20 cm depending on the equipment, thickness of the active layer and the desired accuracy of the interpolation process. The length of the sensor string should be sufficient to extend at least a meter into the permafrost to account for variations in active layer thickness due to climate variability and change. In mountain regions of mid-latitude permafrost, several meters may be required, as a doubling of ALT by several meters has been recorded at some sites in the past decades (e.g. PERMOS 2023). Overall, the thermistor spacing, data collection interval, sensor calibration, and interpolation method are crucial parameters in assessing the accuracy and precision of the active layer estimates (Riseborough, 2008).

Since the near-surface ground thermal regime is highly sensitive to surface disturbance, the disturbance should be minimized during the installation of equipment. Similar to thaw tubes, the estimating of the active layer thickness from temperature measurements effectively comprises only a single point measurement (Smith and Brown, 2009). As a result, the exact location of a thermistor string installation should be determined based on an extensive end-

of-season thaw depth survey by mechanical probing if possible, and the installation point should be representative of the mean end-of-season thaw depth for the entire landscape. If logistically possible, periodic probing surveys timed to coincide with maximum thaw depth are recommended to assess the spatial representativeness of the point measurement. Freeze-thaw processes can result in the vertical movement of the thermistors due to frost heave and/or thaw subsidence resulting in erroneous or inconsistent estimates of the active layer thickness. Measuring the vertical position of the ground surface relative to a stable benchmark, such as thermistor casings embedded in permafrost, can minimize this error.

5. 4.4 MEASUREMENTS OF ROCK GLACIER VELOCITY

5.1. 4.4.1 General

Since the early 2000s, an increasing number of studies are quantifying and/or monitoring the kinematic behavior of rock glaciers, contributing to a better understanding of their motion mechanisms and reaction to climate change (Kellerer-Pirklbauer et al. 2018, PERMOS 2023). In particular, observations show that many rock glaciers within a specific region have a similar interannual to longer term evolution of surface displacement rates, which strongly depends on ground temperature changes (Delaloye et al. 2008, Kääh et al., 2021, Monnier and Kinnard 2017). The monitoring of changes in rock glacier velocity thus provides information about the impact of climate change on creeping mountain permafrost and, indirectly, on its thermal state (Frauenfelder et al. 2003, Staub et al. 2016).

This Section presents the necessary concepts and definitions for the standardized production of Rock Glacier Velocity (RGV) time series. It provides practical recommendations for setting-up long-term RGV monitoring sites as well as a general procedure for producing consistent RGV products from collected kinematic data. The content of this Section was compiled by the IPA (International Permafrost Association) Action Group on Rock glacier inventories and kinematics (RGIK, 2023a, b, c, d).

Here two important clarifications of the terminology adopted in this document:

- *kinematics* describes the general mechanical behavior/processes of rock glaciers in the form of surface and/or internal deformation, and *velocity* refers to the quantifiable variable.
- *creep* or *rock glacier creep* has to be understood as a generic term referring to the variable combination of both internal deformation within the crystalline structure of the frozen ground (creep stricto sensu) and shearing in one or several discrete layers at depth (shear horizon).

4.4.1.1 Definition, Units, Scales

Rock glaciers are defined as debris landforms generated by the former or current creep of permafrost, detectable in the landscape with the following morphologies: steep front and lateral margins and optionally ridge-and-furrow surface topography (RGIK, 2023a).

Rock glacier velocity (RGV) is defined as a time series of annualized surface velocity values expressed in m/a and measured/computed on a rock glacier unit or a part of it. RGV refers to surface velocities related to permafrost creep. The annual surface velocity values, which build up RGV, are called RGV values (RGIK, 2023c).

The *RGV values* are measured/computed from *velocity data* of any dimension (1-3D), which are spatially and/or temporally aggregated following a methodology that must be precisely documented and remain consistent over time (RGIK, 2023c).

The *velocity data* are surface velocity values measured/computed based on *initial data* and expressed in m/a (RGIK 2023d)

The *initial data* are surface velocity, displacement or position data obtained with a specific technique. Depending on the selected technique, initial data may have different geometric references (lagrangian or eulerian), units, dimensions (1-3D) as well as spatial and temporal resolutions (RGIK 2023d).

4.4.1.2 Temporal variability of RGV

The velocity of a rock glacier primarily depends on driving factors such as internal structure, landform geometry, topography, geology, lithology, and debris loading, which often are constant or changing very slowly (excluding rock glaciers affected by glacial processes or rock avalanches). The temporal evolution of rock glacier velocity depends in particular on shifts in ground temperature between the permafrost table and the main shearing horizon, which are constrained by the evolution of the ground surface temperature and impact the rheological and hydrological properties of the frozen ground (e.g., Kääb et al. 2007). The closer to 0°C that the permafrost temperature rises, the faster the rock glacier moves. Hydrological processes related to water infiltration (e.g., changing water content and pore pressure during melt or rain periods), which interact with the internal structure of the rock glacier, can also play a significant role in rock glacier kinematic behavior (e.g., Cicoira et al. 2019).

Three superimposed types of temporal variability in rock glacier velocity have been identified: 1) multi-decennial trend, 2) Interannual variation and 3) Seasonal rhythm.

The multi-decennial behavior (change over several decades) of rock glacier velocities reflects the impact of climate change and responds regionally almost synchronously to changes in permafrost temperatures. A velocity increase by a factor 2 to 10 has been reported for the last decades from various rock glaciers in different regions on Earth (e.g., Pellet et al. 2023). Rock glaciers connected to glaciers appear to have a specific evolution that differs from other types of rock glaciers. At the interannual scale, velocity variations are likely controlled by changes in ground temperature, which are mainly driven by annually fluctuating snow cover insulation as well as air temperature. Such interannual variations can be comparatively large and exceed +/- 50% of the value of the previous year. However, they appear to occur simultaneously and proportionally for many rock glaciers within a region, independent of the activity rate and morphological characteristics (e.g., PERMOS 2023). At a seasonal scale rock glaciers usually exhibit a repetitive landform-specific intra-annual behavior (annual cyclic pattern). Highest velocities are mostly reached after the warm season or in some cases already during the snow ablation period, whereas a decreasing trend occurs throughout the cold season. The amplitude (min-to-max ratio) of the seasonal variations is extremely diverse, ranging almost from 1:1.1 to 1:10 (e.g., Wirz et al. 2016). In comparison to the annual mean velocity, both the landform-specific pattern and relative amplitude have been shown to remain almost constant at a decennial time scale in most documented cases.

Behaviors falling outside of the three types of identified temporal variabilities can occur and are typically associated with site specific conditions not connected to climate forcing. Rock glacier velocities deviating from the common multi-decennial regional trend can be observed. This particularly results from significant changes in the rheology and internal structure of the rock glacier (including ice and water content), in its geometry and interaction with subjacent topography, or in debris loading (including interaction/connection to an eventual glacier or rock avalanches). Such temporal evolution suggests that the rock glacier is typically degrading (i.e., continuously decelerating) or destabilizing (i.e., excessively accelerating). Short term acceleration (of some hours to some weeks) can be observed at the surface of a rock glacier. This reflects either an actual motion related to

permafrost creep (daily variation), or specific movements in the active layer (i.e., block sliding/tilting, etc.). This behavior usually results from a significant input of water in the ground by melting snow or rain.

Given the relation between changes in climate and the multi-decennial and interannual variations in rock glacier velocity, the optimal frequency of observation for climate-oriented time-series is one year. Computing annual velocity time series minimizes the contribution of seasonally dependent processes and short-term variations on the velocity changes, while the repetitiveness of the intra-annual behavior over time allows the exploitation of sub-annual observations. For intra-annual observations, the period considered must remain approximately the same every year and must be long enough (minimum 1 month) to prevent short term (i.e., non-repetitive) variations from influencing the velocity changes.

4.4.1.3 *Spatial variability of RGV*

The displacements observed at the surface of a rock glacier unit build up a spatially coherent flow field due to the motion mechanism of permafrost creep, which is primarily taking place at depths, in the shear horizon (e.g. Haeberli et al. 2006). This flow field often displays a certain degree of spatial heterogeneity, depending on landform-related (e.g., internal structure) and topographical settings. For instance, the movement of the terminal part (front), the lateral margins and the rooting zone are often slower than that of the central part of the rock glacier. The relative velocity changes (i.e., acceleration/deceleration rates in relation to a reference period), however, are usually much more spatially homogeneous. Various processes not related to permafrost creep can alter the spatial homogeneity of the flow field (e.g., subsidence induced by ice melt, movement of isolated boulders).

Rock glacier velocity time series must refer to a consistent flow field representing the downslope movement of a rock glacier unit or a part of it. Considered surface displacements should represent the downslope movement of the rock glacier related to permafrost creep and should not be significantly altered by local disturbing processes (e.g., movement of isolated boulders, subsidence induced by ice melt). Areas affected by such local processes should be avoided for the measurement/computation of the time series. Moreover, rock

glacier monitoring strategies must account for the spatially heterogeneous kinematic behavior within a unit and be adapted accordingly.

Figure 4.4.1. Overview of the spatial and temporal variability of the surface velocity of the Gemmi rock glacier in the Swiss Alps. Annual positions and velocity of four selected boulders are shown for the period 1998-2022 (panels A-D). Advance of the front of the rock glacier is shown based on orthorectified aerial images that were also used to compute the rock glacier average surface velocity starting in 1960 (panel E). The Gemmi RGV time series shown on all velocity plots as reference (gray line) is based on in-situ measurement (aggregation of 5 points

located in the upper center and lower rooting zone areas). Data source: Swiss Permafrost Monitoring Network (PERMOS). Image background: Swisstopo.

5.2. 4.4.2 General principles and requirement

4.4.2.1 Site selection

The motivations for monitoring rock glacier velocities are diverse. In the context of the ECV product, the goal is the generation of long-term time series in a climate-oriented perspective. Therefore, to select suitable sites, the following selection criteria (see also RGIK 2023d) should be assessed based on available data as well as regularly evaluated using newly collected data:

- RGV monitoring must be performed on active or transitional rock glacier units whose deformation mechanism is dominantly related to permafrost creep.
- Rock glaciers with surface movement dominantly caused by other processes than permafrost creep (e.g., ice melt-induced subsidence, landform destabilization) must be avoided.
- Multi-decennial monitoring must appear to be feasible at the selected site.

Over a decadal to multi-decadal time scale, RGV production is/can be limited by various constraints hindering the feasibility of consistent monitoring:

- *Landform constraints:* e.g., development of large scarps (onset of a rock glacier destabilization phase), occurrence of rock falls, instability of surface boulders (rotation, tilt, fall), onset of subsidence induced by ice melt.
- *Technical constraints:* e.g., data availability (e.g., satellite revisit period), data quality (e.g., sensor shift, drift or failure), feasibility of measurements (e.g., not, or partially covered by aerial/satellite images), technological development.
- *Practical constraints:* e.g., site accessibility, safety of people and of equipment, permit for instrumentation and/or field visits.
- *Resource constraints:* e.g., funding, expertise.
- *Processing constraints:* e.g., availability of processing tools, computing power, data property.

A landform should only be selected if decadal to multi-decadal RGV consistency is considered achievable after evaluating the constraints. The constraints listed above may change over time. They may lead to necessary adaptations of the RGV monitoring strategy and thus must be regularly assessed.

4.4.2.2 *Technique selection*

Rock glacier surface velocities can be measured/computed using a wide range of different “techniques”. The term “technique” here refers to available technologies able to provide velocity measurements over rock glaciers and includes the specificities of the sensor, platform and algorithm used for data processing.

Existing techniques range from in-situ surveys (e.g., repeated GNSS field campaigns, permanent GNSS stations) to remote sensing-based approaches (e.g., InSAR, satellite-/air-/UAV-borne photogrammetry, terrestrial laser scanning). Each technique has its own characteristics that affect the temporal and spatial resolution, dimensionality, accuracy, and geometric reference frame of the obtained data. In addition, the spatial and temporal resolution of the data also depends on practical and resource constraints (e.g., cost, workforce). Depending on the site-specific constraints (e.g., topography, location, vegetation, velocity range) not all techniques are suitable for RGV monitoring. Careful evaluation must be performed to determine the most appropriate technique for RGV monitoring on the chosen landforms.

The basic principles and limitations of the most widely used techniques are described in Section 4.3.

4.4.2.3 *Processing steps to produce RGV*

Following the site and technique selection, several steps are necessary to acquire data and transform it into RGV time series, namely:

1. Design of the monitoring setup: definition of the survey design controlling the initial data acquisition and its spatial and temporal resolution.

2. Acquisition of initial data: implementation of the survey design and acquisition of initial data.
3. Preparation of initial data: pre-processing, calibrating and quality-control of initial data.
4. Processing of velocity data: conversion of initial data into surface velocity values and quality control of velocity data.
5. Processing of RGV: spatial and temporal aggregation of velocity data to produce RGV. Spatial and temporal aggregation procedures both include the following stages: velocity data gap-filling, velocity data selection and velocity data aggregation.
6. Evaluation of RGV consistency: evaluation of the consistency throughout all above-mentioned steps and qualitative assessment of the overall RGV consistency.

5.3. 4.4.3 Widely used techniques

4.4.3.1 Terrestrial geodetic survey (TGS)

Terrestrial geodetic survey (TGS) is the most used technique for in-situ measurements of surface rock glacier velocities. TGS are mostly performed using high precision differential GNSS (e.g., Berthling et al. 1998; Lambiel and Delaloye 2004) or theodolites/total stations (e.g., Wahrhaftig and Cox 1959). Both techniques follow the same measurement principle: the positions of a number of observation points spatially distributed over the rock glacier and stable areas next to it are surveyed regularly and the surface velocity is computed from the observed displacements.

Observation points are divided into two categories: survey points located on the rock glacier surface within the moving terrain and control points located on stable areas outside the rock glacier. The survey points, used to measure the surface velocity must be set on large blocks well embedded within the active layer matrix to avoid measuring individual movements of the blocks instead of the general displacement of the creeping body (Lambiel and Delaloye 2004). The control points, used to calibrate and adjust the measured coordinates of the survey points are set in stable terrains outside of the observed landform. Depending on the size and characteristics (i.e., spatial consistency of the flow field, surface characteristics, absolute velocity range) of the surveyed landform, between 10 and 100 points are selected (e.g., PERMOS 2023). The different morphological areas of the rock glacier (i.e., front, lateral margins, rooting zone, central part) should be accounted for as well as any features

specific to the selected landform (i.e., secondary front, subsidence areas, levees, distinct velocity areas). To precisely re-survey the same points, measurement locations are chiseled in the rocks and marked with colored place maker (differential GNSS) or permanent prisms are fixed into the boulders (total station). The typical accuracy of differential GNSS and/or total station measurements is around 1-3 cm (Lambiel and Delaloye 2004).

Figure 4.4.2. Network of points (a, b) measured using terrestrial geodetic survey (c) on the Monte Prosa rock glacier (Switzerland). The resulting annual velocities (d) are shown for all the survey points (in grey) and for the points selected for RGV computation (red). The bold red line represents the RGV time series. Data source: Swiss Permafrost Monitoring Network (PERMOS). Image background: Swisstopo. Photos: Lea Schmid (b) and Reynald Delaloye (c).

TGS are performed at least once a year to obtain annual displacement values (RGIK, 2023c; d). Surveys are performed at approximately the same date each year (± 15 days is

recommended). Surface velocity can be retrieved for each time step in between measurements.

4.4.3.2 Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR)

Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR) is a remote sensing technique that compares satellite radar images acquired at different times to measure ground surface displacements. The procedure starts with the acquisition of complex SAR images. InSAR exploits the phase component of the radar images, related to the sensor-to-ground distance. The user must pay attention to the chosen SAR orbit depending on the slope orientation of the study area. The displacement measurements are along the line-of-sight of the sensor. To avoid underestimating the velocity, viewing geometry aligned with the expected rock glacier creep direction is preferred (Barboux et al. 2014; RGIK, 2023b).

Figure 4.4.3. Dos Linguas rock glacier (Argentinian Andes, a) with the position of the Sentinel-1 InSAR time series (c) and the Sentinel-1 interferogram from 21.04.2017-27.04.2017 (b, $2\pi \Leftrightarrow 2.8\text{cm}$). Background image: Google, DigitalGlobe. Figure adapted from Strozzi et al. 2020.

As snow disturbs the interferometric signal, only summer seasons can effectively be used in cold areas. Depending on the rock glacier of interest, a consistent snow-free observation window has to be chosen. Image pairs (interferograms) are generated with a minimal time interval depending on the revisit time of the satellite (e.g., weekly-monthly for most sensors) and a maximal time interval depending on the rock glacier velocity in respect to the detection capability (half the radar wavelength). Absolute displacements (converted as

annual velocity) are then retrieved using an unwrapping procedure (e.g., Chen and Zebker, 2002) relative to a stable area outside the landform.

Velocity data can be retrieved for each documented InSAR pixel and each unwrapped image pair. Several 10-100 time series can typically be generated. The amount depends on the landform size, the data resolution (10-100 m depending on the sensor) and the extent of areas that are masked by typical InSAR limitations (e.g., shadow, vegetation). Depending on the rock glacier characteristics, advanced multi-temporal InSAR methods, such as SBAS (Berardino, et al. 2002) or PSI (Ferretti, et al. 2001) can also be applied to provide similar velocity time series.

Each initial image pair provides an initial velocity information that may indicate seasonal variability (Strozzi et al., 2020). To document interannual rock glacier velocity, the results are averaged for each season using a consistent observation window (a maximum of ± 15 days of variation is recommended).

4.4.3.3 *Optical imagery*

Feature Tracking Image Correlation is a set of numerical/computer-based techniques that essentially seek to detect and locate similarity patterns between two different images (Scambos et al., 1992). The images used for this purpose are usually acquired by optical sensors (e.g., Landsat), but could also be radar images (Section 4.3.2). Optical sensors can be mounted on different platforms, terrestrial (ground-based photogrammetry), airborne (UAV or planes) and spaceborne (satellite), or even collected manually (Bodin et al., 2018).

The aim of image correlation is to measure the displacement of objects between two images taken at different times, ranging from days, months to several years or even decades (Cusicanqui et al., 2021). To do this, the images must have a common grid reference (same number of rows and columns), the same spatial resolution and the same coordinate system. The classical approach is to find the displacement between two images by optimizing their similarity (Fitch et al., 2002). This is usually done using small windows that allow the displacement to be estimated at different parts of the image.

The result and quality of image correlation using optical images depends firstly on the choice of image correlation parameters, reference, and correlation window size (Debella-Gilo & Kääb, 2011). These parameters must be chosen preferably with prior knowledge of the maximum displacement magnitude of the rock glacier and the pixel-size. A signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) between the maximum similarity value and the average similarity value in the search window serves to evaluate the quality of the correlation (Kääb et al., 2021). In addition, other factors related to the image quality, such as resolution and contrast, affect the quality of the results. The presence of snow, shadows and orthorectification artifacts, could cause some errors during the correlation process. Therefore, images should be carefully selected, preferably during the same period of the year (a maximum of ± 30 days of variation is recommended) to avoid strong surface changes.

Figure 4.4.4. Surface velocity of the Laurichard rock glacier from image aerial optical correlation. The left panel shows the horizontal velocity fields obtained for each time interval. The right panel shows the mean velocities computed for each time interval (blue line) compared to the mean values measured by Terrestrial Geodetic Survey. Image without change from Cusicanqui et al. 2021 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JF006161>) with license “CC BY-ND 4.0”.

The accuracy of the image correlation process has been estimated to be approximately 1/10 of the pixel size approximately (Debella-Gilo & Kääh, 2011). Rock glacier surface velocity fields can be validated using *in-situ* measurement (Vivero et al., 2021). As *in-situ* datasets are not always available, a significant number of stable areas (between 20 and 40% of the image) helps to provide confidence in the uncertainty of the image correlation (Cusicanqui et al., 2023). Velocity data can be retrieved for each pixel of the surface velocity field for the selected image pair. The documented velocity is an average over the entire period. Depending on the image availability and rock glacier characteristics, advanced multi-temporal inversion methods, such as time-series inversion can also be applied to provide velocity time series (Bontemps et al., 2018).

The use of image archives allows for reconstruction of past velocity values and changes. The spatial accuracy may be limited by the image quality and size. This can be compensated for by using a longer time interval. Larger uncertainties are accepted for reconstructions based on image archives (see ECV Requirement sheet).

6. 4.5 SUPPLEMENTARY MEASUREMENTS

Additional measurements are recommended or desirable at or in the vicinity of permafrost monitoring sites. They are used either for indirect monitoring of permafrost conditions, for the interpretation of the permafrost measurements, for modeling of the climate/permafrost relationship, or for site characterization.

Mention: list not complete and will be further extended in the future.

6.1. 4.5.1 Meteorological variables

Permafrost is mainly a temperature dependent phenomenon, and the climate is its main driver. Measuring meteorological variables is therefore necessary to assess the surface energy balance, and to interpret the permafrost temperature, active layer and creep velocity measurements.

The key variables driving the permafrost thermal regime are air temperature, solar radiation and snow cover. Air temperature and solar radiation are the main drivers of the subsurface thermal regime in snow free periods. The timing of the snow cover during winter defines the period during which the subsurface is thermally insulated from the atmospheric processes.

- **Air temperature and solar radiation:** for measurement and processing methods refer to WMO Guide (WMO 2021). If air temperature and/or solar radiation are not measured directly on the site, data can be extrapolated from nearby stations. However, microclimate, local variability and inversion effects must be carefully addressed for the extrapolation of air temperature time series to a permafrost observation site.
- **Snow depth** is an additional driver of permafrost thermal state changes owing to the snow cover's insulating effect, which limits winter heat loss from the ground and modulates the influence of air temperature changes on the ground thermal regime. It should be measured in situ, because of its large spatial variability. For methods, refer to WMO Guide (WMO 2021).

To allow the calculation of the surface energy balance wind speed and direction, relative humidity as well as a full radiation balance (in and outgoing long and short-wave radiation) need also to be measured. (cf. Hoelzle et al. 2022).

The colocated measurement of both cryospheric and meteorological variables (see e.g. Boike et al. 2018; Isaksen et al. 2022; Noetzli et al. 2021) is the key approach promoted by the GCW Cryonet network.

6.2. 4.5.2 Ground surface variables

Many studies reveal an offset between near surface air temperature and ground surface temperature, called "surface offset" (see Figure 4.4.1.1), due to ground surface characteristics, topography or snow cover. The ground surface temperature integrates the surface energy balance and directly drives temperature change in the subsurface thermal regime. It is used as an input variable for ground temperature modeling.

Ground Surface Temperature (GST) is typically measured about one decimeter below the ground surface (Noetzli et al. 2021) with autonomous mini data loggers or individual

temperature sensors connected to a remote data logger. For methods and strategies, see [PermaNET Guidelines](#).

Soil moisture in the active layer can be an explanatory factor of the thermal offset. It should be measured together with ground temperatures in the active layer. For methods, refer to WMO Guide (WMO 2021).

For other standards see WMO Guide (WMO 2021) where measurement depths for single near-surface temperature sensors are at 0.05 m and 0.1 m depth, following the two standard uppermost depths for soil temperature measurements defined by WMO.

On rock glaciers and other coarse blocky ground material, the surface can be difficult to define, such that measurements above about 1 m depth may become unreliable. In these cases, the definition of the surface level needs to be well defined and documented (Noetzli et al. 2021).

6.3. 4.5.3 Geophysical measurements

Making use of the different physical properties of the ground materials, geophysical measurements enable the indirect and non-invasive detection and monitoring of subsurface characteristics from the surface. In permafrost studies, they are commonly used to provide evidence of the presence of ground ice and identify the composition of the subsurface as well as its thermal state (i.e. frozen or unfrozen). Typically, geophysical measurements yield 1-to-3-dimensional information that reaches down to tens of meters depth and covers horizontal distances ranging from several meters up to thousands of meters. A large range of methods and instruments can be applied either for site characterization, or when repeated at regular intervals to assess the temporal evolution of site characteristics and permafrost conditions (e.g. Hauck and Kneisel 2008).

Four main geophysical methods are commonly used in permafrost research, namely electric, electromagnetic, seismic and radar methods (Hauck 2013). These methods are often combined to improve the assessment of the subsurface characteristics (Wagner and

Uhlemann 2021) as well as to quantify the ground water- and ice-content through the application of petrophysical models (e.g., Hauck et al. 2011, Wagner et al. 2019).

- **Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT)** is the most universal geophysical method applied in permafrost monitoring (e.g. PERMOS 2019) and research. It uses the exponential increase of electrical resistivity at the freezing point of water to detect and characterize ice bodies and ice bonded sediment within the subsurface. ERT has been used for decades in the field of permafrost research and detailed methods and strategies can be found in the literature (see e.g. Farzamian et al. 2020, Hauck and Kneisel 2008, Mollaret et al. 2019, Supper et al. 2014). The IPA-supported Action Group “Towards an International Database of Geoelectrical Surveys on Permafrost (IDGPS)” created an international database for ERT data (IDGSP [website](#)) as well as guidelines for measurement repetition and processing (Herring et al. 2023) ERT can be associated with **Induced Polarization (IP)** (e.g., Duvillard et al. 2021) or **Frequency or Time Domain Electro-Magnetometry (FDEM and TDEM)** (e.g., Boaga et al. 2020) to improve the differentiation of frozen and unfrozen terrain.
- **Seismic Refraction Tomography (SRT)** and **Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)** are often used in combination with ERT, as both the seismic P-wave velocity and the transmission of electromagnetic waves are strongly affected by contrasts between frozen and unfrozen substrates. Typical applications include the mapping of the active layer/permafrost interface, internal discontinuities and/or the bedrock profile (e.g. Monnier and Kinnard 2015), as well as the monitoring of ground ice evolution (e.g. Hilbich 2010).

6.4. 4.5.4 Environmental parameters

For Arctic Active Layer sites, environmental parameters like vegetation type, soil, ... are surveyed on CALM grids, in order to serve both for site characterization and as interpretation parameters for explaining the spatial variability of ALT measurements. Guidelines are provided by the CALM protocol.

7. 4.6 REFERENCES

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